

Deliverable D1.3

Updated Project Handbook- V2

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-STEERS: enable federated data visits and large-scale, cross-border analysis in the life sciences by users across the whole European Research Area (101131096)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-STEERS (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01)		
WP No & Title:	WP1 - Coordination and support		
WP leader(s):	Juan Arenas, Nikki Coutts		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	1. ELIXIR Hub		
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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	1. ELIXIR Hub		
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Contributors: N/A			
Acknowledgments (not grant participants):			
Reviewers:	ELIXIR-STEERS Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
20/12/2024	1v1	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Initial updated version
23/12/2024	1v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
31/01/2025	2v0	Nikki Coutts / Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

This report provides an update to the initial version of the ELIXIR-STEERS Project Handbook, shown in Deliverable D1.1¹.

The project handbook follows the Open PM² best practices to provide the board members and the project participants with a clear definition of their roles and responsibilities as well as the relevant processes and assets the project will use to ensure contractual commitments in the Grant Agreement are delivered on time and within the scope and budget and with the expected level of quality.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1.1: Establishment of the governance structure mobilising the project resources and developing the project guidance, taking diversity into account (Task 1.1 & Task 1.5)	Yes
Objective 1.2: Efficient and effective project execution and monitoring, collecting project key performance indicators (KPIs) and tracking risk, issues, and opportunities to assist the project boards on making informed decisions at all levels (Task 1.2)	Yes
Objective 1.3: Evaluation, development and implementation of the data management plan and sustainability plan (Task 1.3 & Task 1.4)	No
Objective 1.4: Increased project management capacity across the ELIXIR Nodes (Task 1.5)	No

3. Introduction

The aim of this deliverable was to provide an update to the initial version of the project handbook following the Open PM² best practices. It was defined that the handbook must provide the board members and the project participants with a clear definition of their roles and responsibilities as well as the relevant processes and assets that the project must use to ensure the contractual commitments as defined in the Grant Agreement are delivered; not only on time but within the scope and budget and with the expected level of quality.

The updated version of the Project Handbook (see Appendix 1) includes details of the new Partners

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/11186819>

and Work Packages added as part of an uplift to the project.

The live version is stored in the ELIXIR-STEERS Google Drive², which all project participants have access to.

4. Description of work accomplished

The description of work accomplished and results have been outlined below.

The finalised Project Handbook 2v0, up to date as of 23rd December 2024, can be viewed in Appendix 1.

The live and evolving Project Handbook can be accessed in Appendix 2.

In Figure 4.1 (below) you can see the Table of Contents used in the Project Handbook which is adapted from the Open PM² template³ using the prior project handbook preparation experience of the Project Management Team. The PM² Methodology originated from the European Commission and Open PM² provides many guidelines and templates to facilitate the management and documentation of EC projects.

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² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18vTAvIIQdes6Vz3LznX0E28dJsWMxMPv>

³

[https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/wikis/display/openPM2/Artefacts?preview=/175357231/351800464/\(\(OPM2-04.P.TPL.v3.0\).Project_Handbook.\(ProjectName\).\(dd-mm-yyyy\).\(vx.x\).docx](https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfis/wikis/display/openPM2/Artefacts?preview=/175357231/351800464/((OPM2-04.P.TPL.v3.0).Project_Handbook.(ProjectName).(dd-mm-yyyy).(vx.x).docx)

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4.1 Update of processes as defined in the Project Handbook

All project participants are welcome to, and actively encouraged to suggest updates to the processes which were defined in the Project Handbook. The Project Handbook is designed to be a living, adaptable resource and therefore, as we refine and define new processes, the Project Handbook must be updated to avoid becoming stagnant and of no help to project partners. The next formal update will be made at Month 24.

5. Conclusions

The project handbook provides the framework for the management of the ELIXIR-STEERS project. The Project Management Team will monitor the relevance of the handbook regularly during the duration of the project and adapt it as required to ensure that it remains relevant, meets the needs of the project participants and fulfils the objectives of the deliverable.

6. Impact

The project handbook and the associated project assets (e.g. the project monitoring tool) will provide the framework for the monitoring and delivery of the tasks and objectives of each of the five work packages at both the technical and financial level.

7. Next Steps

The project handbook will be kept as a live document, available for review and modification at any point during the project duration to ensure it remains a valuable project resource. Project participants will have easy access to the document at all times from the project Google Drive and recommended to rely on it as a first point of contact when they have project management related questions.

8. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable.

Appendix 1: ELIXIR-STEERS Project Handbook 2v0

The project handbook copied here is a snapshot of the updated version as of 23rd December 2024. As the project handbook is a live, and evolving document the latest version can be found linked to from Appendix 2, below.

101131096 - ELIXIR-STEERS

Project Handbook

Date: December 2025

Version: 2v0

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Document Title:	Project Handbook
Project Title:	ELIXIR-STEERS
Document Author:	Nikki Coutts, Juan Arenas, Hannah Hurst
Project Owner:	Andrew Smith
Project Manager:	Nikki Coutts, Juan Arenas
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DOCUMENT HISTORY

The Document Author is authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner. Changes to this document are summarised in the following table.

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes
Vo.1	17/04/24	Nikki Coutts	First draft of full handbook structure
Vo.2	28/04/24	Juan Arenas & Nikki Coutts	Review of draft and closed comments and circulated to MB for review
Vo.3	06/05/24	Nikki Coutts	Final comments closed
V1.0	06/05/24	Nikki Coutts	Finalised to submit as a deliverable
V1.1	20/12/2024	Nikki Coutts	Updates made to Handbook (for D1.3)
V1.2	23/12/2024	Juan Arenas & Nikki Coutts	Reviewed updates, closure of comments and circulated to MB for review
V2.0	31/01/2025	Nikki Coutts, Mado Fernandez	Finalised to submit as a deliverable

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1. ABOUT THE PROJECT HANDBOOK

The Project Handbook provides a complete overview of the management and administrative procedures and principles to ensure an efficient execution of the ELIXIR-STEERS project, thus contributing to the production of high quality project results. The Project Handbook documents the selected approach for implementing the project goals, including the milestones and deliverables and relevant KPIs. It also highlights the key controlling processes to be used, the project policies and rules, and the overall management approach, including, but not limited to management structure, tasks, decision-making procedures, responsibilities and roles.

The Project Handbook is an important document since it contains all relevant planning information that the consortium partners will use as a framework for delivery during the course of the project.

The Project Handbook becomes the basis for managing the project throughout its lifecycle and is an important point of reference for all consortium partners and stakeholders. The Project Handbook is kept up to date throughout the life of the project through annual updates.

Language adopted throughout the documents aims to be clear and concise.

Please note that this Project Handbook is circulated as a guidance document only. It should not be relied upon for making any legal assessments, for which Beneficiaries should always refer to the Grant Agreement (including its annexes)⁴ and the Consortium Agreement⁵.

2. PROJECT OVERVIEW

2.1. Basic Project Information

Project Call:

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01 - Developing, consolidating and optimising the European research infrastructures landscape, maintaining global leadership (2023)

Project Title: Enable federated data visits and large-scale, cross-border analysis in the life sciences by users across the whole European Research Area.

Project Acronym: ELIXIR-STEERS

Grant Agreement N°: 101131096

Call topic: HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-03

⁴ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LflWNZjgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

⁵ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WH6aOvzrOQsmly5UyKHWG7fx4yR2Qk0/view?usp=drive_link

Project start date: 1st February 2024
 Project end date: 31st January 2026
 Duration: 36 months
 Project budget: €4,000,000.00
 Number of Beneficiaries: 32 (to become 34 in January 2025)
 Number of LTPs: 2
 Number of APs: 3 (to become 1 in January 2025)

2.2. Short Names of the Consortium Partners

Table 1. Beneficiaries

Beneficiary n°	Name of the consortium partner	Short name
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	EMBL/ELIXIR
2	VIB VZW	VIB
3	KYPRIAKO IDRYMA EREVNON GIA TI MYIKI DISTROFIA	CING
4	UNIVERSITY OF CYPRUS	UCY
5	USTAV ORGANICKE CHEMIE A BIOCHEMIE, AV CR, V.V.I.	UOCHB
6	ALBERT-LUDWIGS-UNIVERSITAET FREIBURG	UFR
7	TARTU ULIKOOL	UTARTU
8	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC
9	CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	CSC
10	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	INRAE
11	BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES RESEARCH CENTER ALEXANDER FLEMING	BSRCAF
12	ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS	ATHENA RC
13	HELLENIC PASTEUR INSTITUTE	HPI

14	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH
15	SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU MEDICINSKI FAKULTET	UZSM
16	TERMEZETTUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT	HUN-REN TTK
17	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	UCD
18	WEIZMANN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE	WEIZMANN
19	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR
20	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	UNIPD
21	PNED GIE	PNED
22	STICHTING HEALTH-RI	HEALTH-RI
23	UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN	UiB
24	UNIVERSITETET I TROMSOE - NORGES ARKTISKE UNIVERSITET	UiT
25	ASSOCIACAO BIP4DAB	biodata.pt
26	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	UU
27	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI	UL
28	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC
29	SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET	SDU
30	KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH
34	UNIVERSITAT WIEN	UV
35	CLUSTERUL ROMAN DE BIOINFORMATICA	CRB

2.3. Project Acronyms

Table 2. Project Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CA	Consortium Agreement - Agreement concluded amongst ELIXIR-STEERS Beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.
CDA	Confidential Disclosure Agreement
Consortium	The ELIXIR-STEERS Consortium, comprising the named legal entities.
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement - The agreement signed between the Beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the ELIXIR-STEERS project
IC	Indirect Costs
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
ODC	Other direct costs
PM	Project Manager
PMs	Person months
PMT	Project Management Team
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
QA	Quality Assurance

WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

2.4. Project Summary

ELIXIR unites Europe’s leading life science organisations in managing and safeguarding the increasing volume of data being generated by publicly funded research. It coordinates, integrates and sustains bioinformatics resources across its 23 Nodes. ELIXIR enables users in academia and industry to access services (databases, software, training, standards, compute) provided through national Nodes. ELIXIR is the ESFRI Landmark for life science data and plays a unique role in the landscape, with millions of users globally, supporting the digital-needs of other ESFRIs and Horizon Europe research projects.

Increasingly, life-science data is held at national and institutional centres. Thus, large-scale data analytics requires that researchers can find and analyse data distributed across Europe. The purpose of ELIXIR-STEERS is to build capacity for large-scale, cross-border data analysis and for this capacity to be embedded across member states. ELIXIR-STEERS directly benefit Europe’s life scientists by allowing software and workflows to meet requirements of those using them in national centres. A ‘robust, reproducible and green’ approach to software and workflow provision will ensure that scientists have access to high quality, energy-efficient analysis tools. The project will also develop the crediting and recognition systems for software, supporting improvements to research assessment frameworks.

Further, ELIXIR-STEERS supports ELIXIR’s long-term operations by addressing the recommendations of the European Commission and ESFRI on the long-term sustainability of research infrastructures. It will strengthen the operational excellence of ELIXIR’s Nodes; support the training and development of professional and scientific staff in ELIXIR Nodes; expand the membership of ELIXIR to new countries, especially widening countries; enable international collaborations in particular with Latin America and Africa; and stimulate innovation and industry engagement.

2.5. Project Scope and Work Structure

The methodological approach for ELIXIR-STEERS is to utilise existing ELIXIR structures to bring people together whenever possible. This ensures maximum benefit from previous EU and ELIXIR MS funding that established these structures and helps to support the sustainability of ELIXIR-STEERS outputs once the project has concluded. The themes within ELIXIR-STEERS - software and workflows, Node development, training, communications, and industry engagement - touch on several existing operational structures within ELIXIR. The ELIXIR Tools and Training Platforms, for example, bring together ELIXIR’s experts in the areas of software development (WP2-3) and training (WP4) respectively. As the size of ELIXIR far exceeds the

opportunity for engagement in INFRADEV-3, using existing structures to share information, best practice and visibility will also ensure that ELIXIR experts beyond those involved in ELIXIR-STEERS also benefit from learnings.

ELIXIR-STEERS also draws on other working groups, for instance ELIXIR’s Focus Groups for Machine Learning (WP2), Communications (WP5) and Industry (WP5) will provide wider networks of Node experts to adopt ELIXIR-STEERS outputs. In addition, the ELIXIR Node Coordinators Group will connect to Node development tasks (WP4).

Figure 1. ELIXIR-STEERS will utilise existing ELIXIR structures.

Table 3. Work Package Titles

Work package #	Title
WP1	Coordination and support
WP2	Implementation of research software best practices through ELIXIR Communities
WP3	Infrastructure services to enable adoption and deployment of software best practices
WP4	Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training

WP5	Communications, outreach, industry and international
WP6	EC mandated Ethics Requirements

A budget has been held back (via WP1) to distribute to a lead entity in any new countries that join ELIXIR during the duration of ELIXIR-STEERS. This pragmatic approach reflects the reality of not being able to predict exactly when a country will join and the need to have a mechanism in place to engage and support that country when they do join. This approach comes with the full support of the respective Ministries in the countries that are close to joining ELIXIR. Once members of ELIXIR-STEERS, those institutes, which are largely in EU-13 countries, will benefit from the capacity building activities within ELIXIR-STEERS for national coordination (WP4) and software development (WP2-3).

ELIXIR-STEERS will also utilise links with other community efforts entirely separate from ELIXIR, including representative organisations for particular scientific domains such as NuGO for the food and nutrition domain, the COST Action ML4NGP for Intrinsically Disordered Proteins and 3D-Bioinfo and EASyM for the systems biology community. Broader stakeholder groups such as RDA will be engaged by ELIXIR-STEERS representatives.

ELIXIR-STEERS will optimise frequently used software to enable efficient utilisation of life science computation, providing the most recent versions and instances of software at the pan-European scale in order to reduce energy consumption at the same time as helping scientists answer important biomedical questions.

As part of the ELIXIR-STEERS project deals with the adoption of best-practices for research software and workflows, we will advocate for the wider adoption of the DOME⁶ recommendations. This can lead to refinements of DOME for selected ELIXIR Communities, to capture field-specific differences. As such, ELIXIR-STEERS is devoted to the adoption of more robust, reproducible, and reliable AI. Given the wide usage of AI in the life sciences, it is likely that AI activities in other research projects will be enabled by the activities of ELIXIR-STEERS such as through the benchmarking of workflows. Any AI method to be employed and/or developed as part of ELIXIR-STEERS is however foreseen to be in TRLs 1-3, and so limited to research and development prototypes. These will be safeguarded by using the DOME recommendations. Further, any application beyond TRL-3 will be flagged in the project and brought to the Management Board (MB) for assessment and appropriate actions to be taken.

Computational biology is an increasingly interdisciplinary endeavour and ELIXIR-STEERS is constructed to enable interdisciplinarity at all levels, from the experts involved in the project, to the projects, communities and initiatives that will be engaged. Input and recommendations will be sought from a range of existing Horizon Europe projects, in particular, EOSC-related projects in relation to the development of WP3. WP2 will work with several different ELIXIR Communities to understand their needs including IDP, 3D-BioInfo, Biodiversity, Systems Biology and Single Cell

⁶ Walsh, I., Fishman, D., Garcia-Gasulla, D. et al. DOME: recommendations for supervised machine learning validation in biology. Nat Methods 18, 1122–1127 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01205-4>; DOME-ML website: <https://dome-ml.org/>

Omics. These ELIXIR Communities bring together ELIXIR experts as well as experts from organisations outside ELIXIR including from other ESFRI RIs. They also often allow linking with important community driven EU projects (e.g., BGE for the Biodiversity community). This is critical because the software and workflow development best practices developed by ELIXIR-STEERS should be relevant to and adapted by life scientists working nationally and through other related EU research projects.

In terms of expertise within the consortium, ELIXIR-STEERS brings together a range of experts from different yet interconnected domains including software developers (WP2-3), bioinformaticians (WP2-3), trainers (WP4), Node development staff (WP4), industry engagement staff (WP5), communications officers (WP5), external relations experts (WP5) and project managers (WP1). Monthly ELIXIR-STEERS project meetings and internal communications channels will enable the cross-fertilisation of ideas and knowledge between these various project partners.

2.6. Project Coordination and Management

Work Package 1 (Coordination & Support) will establish effective project governance and internal communication procedures to allow for the flow of information within the project. It will also fulfil the administrative tasks associated with management of the project.

The overall goal of this WP is to oversee the project execution ensuring the project goals are fully accomplished within the expected scope, timeframe, and resources and with the required level of quality. Risk, issues, and opportunities will be monitored to maximise the benefit delivered and processes will be in place to identify project outputs that will need to be sustained beyond the life-time of the project.

The Work Package sets out 4 clear objectives:

- 1) Establishment of the governance structure mobilising the project resources and developing the project guidance, taking diversity into account (Task 1.1 & Task 1.5)
- 2) Efficient and effective project execution and monitoring, collecting project key performance indicators (KPIs) and tracking risk, issues, and opportunities to assist the project boards on making informed decisions at all levels (Task 1.2)
- 3) Evaluation, development and implementation of the data management plan and sustainability plan (Task 1.3 & Task 1.4)
- 4) Increased project management capacity across the ELIXIR Nodes (Task 1.5)

All tasks will contribute to the incremental version of the Project Handbook that will define and update the different plans and processes, including a yearly evaluation that will collect metrics and lessons learned along with the project execution to contribute to the continuous improvement of ELIXIR's EC funded projects.

3. PROJECT APPROACH

3.1. Required Project Documentation

Table 4. Required Project Documentations

Artefact	Yes/No	Location	If No, briefly explain the reason
Description of Action - Part A	✓	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jyXDwrc-XutNWieaaynkaHTnhrcAauzV/view?usp=drive_link	
Description of Action - Part B	✓	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1j5BhfCgcFSokqm1igw9S1XCbkuSnjJ8S/view?usp=drive_link	
Grant Agreement	✓	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-igaOg8NpWo_OpnL8LfiWNZJgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link	
Consortium Agreement - fully executed	✓	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WH6aOvzrQOsmly5IUyKHWG7fx4yR2Qk0/view?usp=drive_link	
Project Handbook (this document)	✓	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bcB9lt5r_1lfPVeFCzgLUyoY3zKKEGAlHfCbhFLYZug/edit	
Project Monitoring File	✓	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbigerFIFABmD5VQM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126	
Data Management Plan	✓	https://zenodo.org/records/12707053	
Other...			

3.2. Internal Conflict Resolution and Escalation

Conflicts are situations in which one or both parties perceive a threat. They are considered to be critical issues and can be raised by any of the project stakeholders. The Project Management Team should proactively identify, log and raise such issues for resolution.

In the event that an internal conflict arises at a given time, the project coordination and the management structure is formulated to support a bottom-up approach with respect to its resolution.

- Conflicts amongst Beneficiaries in any given activity will be discussed at the Work Package (WP) level with the help of the respective Work Package Leaders (WPLs).
- If unresolved, the issue will escalate to the Managing Board (MB), which, with the help of the PMT will use mediation to objectively aim to solve the issue.
- If unresolved and when the issue is significant enough, the Managing Board could then make a proposal to the Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN) to amicably resolve the issue. In case no solution can be found which is acceptable to the Beneficiaries involved in the dispute, the dispute resolution mechanisms of the Consortium Agreement will apply.

At all stages, Beneficiaries can reach out to the PMT in case they feel a request has not been adequately dealt with.

4. PROJECT PROCESSES

4.1. Risk Management

4.1.1. Risk Identification and categorization

An initial list of key project risks has been identified during the preparation of the Action and a respective table of identified risks can be found on page 31 of the DoA - Part A⁷.

All Beneficiaries are asked to screen their activities with regards to additional new risks and to promptly notify the PMT of any significant new risk(s) having the potential to affect the completion of the assigned WP.

4.1.2. Risk Assessment, registry and action plan

The PMT will add any new risks, including a description of the possible impact, to the risk log⁸ within the Project Monitoring file⁹ and bring any additional risk(s) to the attention of the MB who will discuss categorization and prioritisation.

Prioritisation of the risks will be based on the possible impact (I) and the probability (II) of realisation of the risk. Based on the prioritisation appropriate mitigation activities and/or contingency plans will be developed.

An action plan for each identified risk has to be developed by the concerned work package and agreed by the MB as part of the risk management process. The list of identified risks are stored in the STEERS Google Shared Drive, the agreed Document management system for the project.

⁷ Risks. P31: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1jyXDwrc-XutNWieaaynkaHTnhrcAauzV/view?usp=drive_link

⁸ Risk Log:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=915549057>

⁹ Project Monitoring file:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1662215412>

The risk log¹⁰ will be maintained and reviewed on a 3-monthly basis during the Managing Board calls.

4.1.3. Risk monitoring

All identified risks and mitigation steps will be reviewed by the MB on a quarterly basis during their monthly TC. WPLs and Task leads are asked to actively contribute to this activity which will be overseen by the Project Coordinator and PMT.

An update of the risk assessment activity, including the major risks identified with their corresponding mitigation and contingency plans, will be included in the Periodic Reports to be annually submitted to the European Commission. This will include information on newly identified risks and risks which have been resolved.

WP₁ will drive the risk management process, dealing with the identification, assessment and follow-up of threats and opportunities likely to affect the project performance as a whole.

For any questions related to project risks, contact STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org.

4.2. Issue Management

The project issue management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, prioritising, assigning, resolving and controlling issues. It is a four step process that the Project Management Team (PMT) executes whenever required throughout the project lifecycle:

- **Issue Identification:** Issues can be identified by any project stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, using different communication channels such as meetings and emails (STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org). The issues are registered in the Issues Log¹¹.
- **Issue Assessment and Action Recommendation:** a first informal assessment by PMT, considers the category, impact, urgency and size of the issue, followed by a more detailed analysis to identify the root cause and recommend a solution. This information is documented in the Issues Log and used as input to the appropriate decision makers (based on the escalation process). The decision is documented in the Decision Log.
- **Actions Implementation:** After issues are evaluated and the remediation actions approved, the Project Management Team will incorporate these actions into the appropriate project related documentation such as the next amended Description of Action and logs.
- **Issue Control:** During the regular Project Management meetings the status of issues and related actions will be revised, and new issues identified. Additionally, PMT will report monthly the status of the major issues to the Managing Board and, when appropriate, to other project stakeholders.

¹⁰ Risk Log:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VOM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=915549057>

¹¹ Issues Log:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VOM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1037062273>

For any questions related to project issues, contact:
STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org.

4.3. Project Change Management

The project change management process defines the activities related to identifying, documenting, assessing, approving, prioritising, planning and controlling changes, and communicating them to all relevant stakeholders. It is a five step process that the Project Management Team (PMT) executes whenever required throughout the project lifecycle:

- **Change Identification:** a request for a change can be submitted formally via an email to PMT (STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org), or can be identified and raised during meetings as a result of decisions, issues or risks. The requested change should then be captured in the Change Log¹² including information to identify the change, such as the requestor, a short description, identification date, etc.
- **Change Assessment and Action Recommendation:** the size and impact of the change on the project scope, schedule, cost, quality, risk, and other project boundaries is assessed, whereafter a recommended action will be documented by PMT in the Change Log.
- **Change Approval:** the approval of a project change will be determined by the size and scope of the change requested. For low impact change requests which do not require formal approval by the EC, PMT will advise who must approve the change, be it PMT, the Managing Board or the ELIXIR-STEERS HoN Committee. If a formal change to the Grant Agreement is required then the PMT will use the information provided in the Change Log as an input to the formal amendment request that will be submitted to the EC. Only when a significant change is requested or a number of smaller requests have been received, will an amendment request be submitted to the EC, with no more than one amendment request per year.
- **Change Implementation:** the activities related to the implementation of approved changes will be documented in the Project Monitoring File¹³.
- **Change Control:** new or open changes will be identified/reassessed during the weekly Project Management Meeting and during the Managing Board monthly meeting when needed.

4.4. Quality Management

The implementation and execution of ELIXIR-STEERS follows the principles of Horizon Europe and European Commission (EC) rules and are more specifically defined in the Grant Agreement, the Description of Action and in the Consortium Agreement provisions. The procedures described in this section shall not replace any of the established agreements within the consortium or with the EC, or any of the EC guidelines for project implementation. The project will be managed according to EC best practice with a dedicated communications effort.

¹² Change Log:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1dnASFY7bErUPIPQ28Sxuj-R9MyHPXpWAGgIMaClqqCU/edit#gid=942104258>

¹³ Project Monitoring file:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6lnrFOW1idF5AF/edit?pli=1#gid=1662215412>

The Quality policy is based on the principles of Horizon Europe and the EC rules related to scientific and operational quality; and will take into account the principles for Quality Management and Quality Assurance as laid down in the ISO 9000 framework.

Quality and its pursuit are regarded as important for every individual activity within the project. Criteria and quality standards of both the results of the project and the processes involved in their production need to be assured throughout the entire project.

ELIXIR-STEERS will explore the establishment and operation of a suite of high-quality communications channels, periodic project monitoring including work plan execution, quality assurance, data management, finance execution, innovation management activities, communication and risks.

ELIXIR-STEERS quality objectives are to:

- Ensure that all the project related activities and deliverables are fulfilling highest scientific and technical quality expectations and are following available quality and compliance standards issued by the EC under the Horizon Europe funding scheme.
- To define the measures and the tools to be implemented by all consortium partners to meet these objectives and to provide support to partners to achieve high quality and to monitor adherence to the quality standards set for the project, in alignment with the DoA.
- Provide information on the processes in place to identify and manage major project risks.
- Ensure compliance with agreed Horizon Europe and EC rules, applicable law and regulations, incl. but not limited to data privacy, handling of funds and ethics.

According to Horizon Europe rules the Project Coordinator is also asked to promote gender equality in the project and science and society issues related to the research activities conducted within the project. The gender dimension will be further explored by WP1 in Task 1.5.

4.4.1. Quality policy

The generic quality policy adopted by ELIXIR-STEERS builds upon the following set of principles:

- Quality and its pursuit are regarded as important for every individual activity within the project.
- Criteria and standards by which the quality of both the results of the project and the processes involved in their production will be identified.
- Description of the tools, methods and techniques to be employed in order to ensure quality will be prepared.
- Allowance must be made for monitoring quality during the process and recording compliance and deviation.

Taking into consideration the overall quality policy, high quality standards are to be applied to all the work undertaken throughout the project.

4.4.2. Project quality control

The overall quality control of the project results includes the coordination of quality review for deliverables, prior to their submission to the EC.

It is crucial for the project to ensure that deliverables, as official results of the project, are reviewed and checked for quality. This may also apply to other outcomes of the project that are addressed to parties external to the project.

The present document is focusing only on the general methods implemented to ensure quality of written materials delivered to the EC and other partners external to the Consortium. A document produced in a project generally aims to provide information concerning the work, its progress or the derived results. Each document should thus be carefully drafted with rich content, a clear structure and a professional presentation. The three basic aspects for building quality into project documents are content, appearance and timing. It is generally accepted that the relative importance of each document varies, and it is important that overzealous quality criteria do not compromise timing if marginal benefit to the project is minimal.

For more information about the process, see section 7.1.3. Deliverable review process.

4.5. Configuration Management

4.5.1. Storage of project management artefacts

The Project Management Team have created a structured STEERS Google Shared Drive to store the project management artefacts following the same folder convention per sub-folder. For any assistance with creating new folders, please contact STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org.

4.5.2. Naming convention of project management artefacts

The latest version of a detailed, controlled Documents Version Policy outlining the project naming conventions and other configuration management guidance will be included in D6.2 Data Management Plan.

4.5.3. Versioning of project management artefacts

All project management artefacts are under version control, except for the project logs and checklists.

4.6. Communications Management

The communications management process determines how to communicate most efficiently and effectively to the various stakeholders. It defines and documents the communication items content, format, frequency, the audience and expected results. It also defines how to

communicate project status and the assignment of activities to the various stakeholders, and the communication strategy for each stakeholder, based on their interests, expectations and influence in the project.

For more detailed information and guidance, please review the ELIXIR Communication Strategy¹⁴.

The project meetings identified in Table 5 below will be organised.

Table 5. Project Meetings

Meeting	Chair	Frequency
Project Kick-off Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Once
Project Management Meetings	Project Management Team (PMT)	Weekly
Work Package Team Meetings	Work Package Leaders (WPLs)	weekly - monthly dependent on WP needs
Managing Board Meetings	Project Management Team (PMT)	Monthly (TC) Annually (F2F)
General Assembly	Project Management Team (PMT)	Annually
Outreach and Dissemination meetings	Project Management Team (PMT)	Bi-annually
Industry engagement events	Project Management Team (PMT)	Annually
Mid-term Review Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Once
Change Control Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Ad Hoc
Project-End Review Meeting	Project Management Team (PMT)	Once

The project reports listed in Table 6 below will be delivered.

Table 6. Project Reports.

Report	Responsible	Frequency
Periodic financial report	Project Coordinator	M18/M36

¹⁴ <https://elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-communications-strategy>

Periodic technical report	Project Coordinator	M18/M36
Ethics Report	Ethics Advisor	M18/M36 with Technical report
Project Status report	Work Package Leaders (WPLs)	Monthly (during WPL TC)
Project-End Report	Project Coordinator	With Project-End Review

4.6.1. Communication Plan

The ELIXIR-STEERS consortium will adopt the following approach to communications:

- Use of electronic mail as the main tool for communication within the consortium.
- Use of Slack as a less formal communication method where teams request it (as of February 2024, channels are available for each Work Package)
- Documentation of discussions, agreements and decisions made by phone is encouraged. Specifically, phone conferences should always have an agenda and minutes, which should be made available through the STEERS Google Shared Drive.
- Several distribution lists have been initially created which can be used by any participant depending on the subject of the message. Additional lists may be created as the project evolves, if necessary. ELIXIR will be responsible for updating the below-mentioned lists with the information received from participants. When a list is used, care should be taken by participants to use the "reply to all" feature only when relevant. The table below shows the distribution lists created by the time of publishing this Handbook.

Table 7. Distribution Lists

Distribution list	Description
STEERS-admin@elixir-europe.org	STEERS PIs + admin contacts + STEERS PMT
STEERS-finance@elixir-europe.org	STEERS finance contacts + STEERS PMT
STEERS-legal@elixir-europe.org	STEERS legal contacts + STEERS PMT
STEERS-all@elixir-europe.org	All people involved in STEERS: PIs + team members, admin, legal, finance + STEERS PMT
STEERS-PIs@elixir-europe.org	All STEERS PIs + deputies (if requested) + STEERS PMT
STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org	Nikki, Mado, Juan, Andy
STEERS-scientific@elixir-europe.org	All STEERS scientific partners (signed up to WPs mailing lists) + STEERS PMT

STEERS-WP1@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + STEERS PMT
STEERS-WP2@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + STEERS PMT
STEERS-WP3@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + STEERS PMT
STEERS-WP4@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + STEERS PMT
STEERS-WP5@elixir-europe.org	WPLs, Deputy WPLs, all WP team members + STEERS PMT
STEERS-WPLs@elixir-europe.org	WPLs + deputies if requested + STEERS PMT
STEERS-info@elixir-europe.org	General enquiries (external)
STEERS-externalexperts@elixir-europe.org	External experts (not project partners)

4.6.2. Email guidelines

Good practice when using email is essential.

- Mails should be tagged when action is required (ACTION REQUIRED, FEEDBACK REQUIRED).
- Participants must respond promptly to any email received. When that is not possible, at least acknowledgement of receipt of all messages is strongly recommended, especially when answering an explicit request.
- Carefully consider whether “reply to all” is required.
- All emails sent to any of the mailing lists created so far should start with “STEERS:” in the subject section and senders should add the subject of the message.
- When individual messages between participants are exchanged, use of the same tag is strongly encouraged (e.g. STEERS: WPL meeting_agenda).
- Messages need to be concise but clear, especially when requests are made.
- Message text should include the content needed for the recipient to action the requests
- Deadlines must be made explicit.
- No relevant issues for the work to be performed should remain unclear.

4.6.3. File Exchange and Repository

A Google Shared Drive instance has been created for ELIXIR-STEERS, to be used as a repository of relevant information and files, which facilitates the exchange of documents within the consortium (i.e. meeting minutes, documents in progress, final versions and other relevant reports or announcements). The ELIXIR-STEERS Google Shared Drive also provides the possibility of discussion between participants through messages, maintenance of a calendar of meetings and events, upload of files, and tracking of important milestones and events at both the project and Work Package level.

- All Beneficiaries have been enabled access to the ELIXIR-STEERS Google Shared Drive once they have signed up to the mailing lists. New accesses can be requested by filling in the registration form¹⁵
- The latest version of the ELIXIR-STEERS contact list is uploaded on the STEERS Google Shared Drive, in the Registered Contacts section of the Project Monitoring spreadsheet¹⁶. The up-to-date participants' contact information with clear information of who is included in every mailing list mentioned above will be based on the periodic updates by each of the Work Package Leaders.
- The use of de facto standards based on MS Office-compatible files for electronic document exchange among participants is required when possible. PDF format can alternatively be used to avoid excessive size of files when no editing is required.

ELIXIR-STEERS uses Google Shared Drive as a project management tool that is simultaneously used as a document management system. The ELIXIR-STEERS Google Shared Drive provides a place to store, secure and organise the consortium documentation which helps to ultimately control the quality of documents and conformity of processes.

The tool has capabilities available to set permissions on a file or folder. These clear access rights can be rapidly degraded or defeated entirely by the sysadmin (coordinator) of the consortium. Users with proper visibility rights and access permission can fuel quality control of the project.

Additionally, a document version history is an efficient way to track who has edited files and when. This platform allows users to revert to an earlier version if the file becomes corrupted or if errors are introduced.

With the notification feature available, each person with permission can invite other consortium participants on document edits and to track changes to a document stored in a shared folder simultaneously.

ELIXIR-STEERS uses Google Shared Drive to manage quality of the documents and processes by enhancing the centralization of digital assets, promote maintenance of quality and support backup and data protection.

Any publication in ELIXIR-STEERS is governed by Article 29 of the Grant Agreement and Article 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement. Scientific Publications and Communication to the public are covered by the Communication Plan (section 4.6.1, above) created by WP5.

The Documents Versioning Policy outlined in Section 4.5.2. (Configuration Management), is key to clean and consistent archiving; especially towards the mid/end phase of the project when an increasing number of digital outputs and documents are created. Using the same tag for email

¹⁵Registration form:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfa7J2N195O4HRWxlOnGKaw0X8Z7WzWqnOM_taV6hONHUtilw/viewform

¹⁶ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6InrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1726970740>

subjects and for the documentations in attachments, fuels clear communication and leads to reduced email burden and duplication of work.

4.6.4. Dissemination

Dissemination is an important activity for all EC projects, a fact that is recognised in the project Grant Agreement¹⁷, which requires that we make our scientific work and results openly available, as early as possible and in a form that is easily accessible, understandable and reusable.

All partners must follow the dissemination circulation procedure set out in Clause 8.4.1.1 of the Consortium Agreement¹⁸.

The Commission also provide a Horizon Europe guide to communicating EU research and innovation for project participants¹⁹.

4.6.5. Open Access policy and requirements

Annex 5 of the EC Annotated Model Grant Agreement (AMGA)²⁰ details the obligations related to the provision of open access to scientific publications.

We must ensure open access (free, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to our ELIXIR-STEERS project results.

Further explanations can be found in the EC Annotated Model Grant Agreement. The EC have also prepared the following guide to help steer this process.

Published articles (peer-reviewed or not) have to be submitted to PMT in PDF format. The document(s) will be made available to the consortium on the ELIXIR-STEERS Google Shared Drive in the Articles folder²¹ and listed in the publications and dissemination tab of the reporting tracker spreadsheet²².

4.6.6. EU Funding Acknowledgement

As set out in Article 17.2 of the Grant Agreement²³, unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the STEERS project (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) display the EU emblem and

To be used for ELIXIR-STEERS:

¹⁷https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LfIWNZJgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

¹⁸ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WH6aOvzrOQsmly5lUyKHWG7fx4yR2Ok0/view?usp=drive_link

¹⁹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

²¹ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1C7dW7psmHffm74MZLAogSGWWDBLcexpK?usp=drive_link

²² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1UjKvk6CzyyusDw9Z0HTlkvp9g9pADHydwHC3xNdo84/edit#gid=2128340078>

²³ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LfIWNZJgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

- Download the EU emblem²⁴ in different versions and formats
- When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.
- For the purposes of our obligations under Article 17.2 of the GA, the Beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

(b) include the following text:

ELIXIR-STEERS acknowledgement:

For communication activities:

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101131096".

For infrastructure, equipment and major results:

"This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101131096".

If it is not possible to use this exact statement (e.g. if numerous grants are cited), please ensure that at least the grant's name (ELIXIR-STEERS) and the grant agreement number (101131096) are specified in the Acknowledgements or Funding Statement of the publication, as this helps with detecting articles using text-mining.

- A formal acknowledgement of EC support

Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility: Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

ELIXIR-STEERS disclaimer:

This communication reflects the views of the authors and neither the European Union or any Associated Partners are liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

²⁴ https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en

4.6.7. Project Branding

The ELIXIR-STEERS project must follow the ELIXIR branding and communication guidelines. The ELIXIR branding guidelines, font and project logo are all available on the project Google Shared Drive²⁵.

The branding and style guide should be used in all project communications without alteration. For any questions related to branding and communications please contact Elaine Harrison, elaine.harrison@elixir-europe.org.

Figure 1. The ELIXIR-STEERS logo

4.6.8. Project Website

The project web pages²⁶ are housed on the ELIXIR website and provide an overview of the project, consortium and Board members, and the project timeline. In addition, visitors can find details of upcoming events, and our project outputs. Publications, press releases and submitted public deliverables are also available via the site.

For any updates to the project website, contact Prithviraj Mitra (prithviraj.mitra@elixir-europe.org) or Debbie van Wyk (deborah.vanwyk@elixir-europe.org).

²⁵ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1vu_ZwieAU2SHNIQZFIH4J_ptvmSdvEKH

²⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects/steers>

4.6.9. Social Media

ELIXIR-STEERS does not have dedicated social media accounts, instead, the ELIXIR accounts will be used with dedicated project hashtags on the following platforms:

Twitter: #ELIXIR_STEERS

LinkedIn: #ELIXIR_STEERS

4.6.10. Weekly Brief

The ELIXIR Hub publishes a weekly email update called the Weekly Brief. All STEERS project partners who have signed up to receive this have now been added to the mailing list and receive it weekly on a Monday morning. Every issue provides the recipient with the option to update their preferences or unsubscribe from the list. Content for the Brief is gathered by the ELIXIR Hub communications team. All project partners are encouraged to suggest any project content ideas either by email to the communications team or during the monthly Programme TCs/Managing Board TCs.

Content ideas can be emailed to info@elixir-europe.org.

4.6.11. Templates

Presentations for internal or external communication should use the ELIXIR-STEERS PowerPoint/Google Slide template.

All internal and external documents should use the ELIXIR-STEERS Word/Google Doc template.

All templates are available on the ELIXIR-STEERS Google Shared Drive in the Templates folder²⁷.

All presentations, posters, media briefings and event documentation should display the European flag, besides the project logo. In line with the European Commission's policy on corporate visual identity, Horizon Europe is being promoted as a verbal brand, meaning no 'visual mark' or logotype is needed. More information about displaying the correct logos and funding acknowledgements can be found in the EU Funding Acknowledgement section above, but for any questions, contact should be made with Elaine Harrison, elaine.harrison@elixir-europe.org.

A deliverable template has been prepared and can be found in the Templates folder on the ELIXIR-STEERS Google Shared Drive²⁸, but please note that an individually tailored template has been created by the Project Management Team for all project deliverables and linked within the 'Commitments' tab of the ELIXIR-STEERS Project Monitoring spreadsheet²⁹. All Deliverable Authors shall use the approved deliverable template for the production of deliverables. For more information about how to prepare a deliverable report, please see section 7.1. (Deliverable).

²⁷ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/19-rq9NSiHjCpU5MLsCKMUeUJz7wf35Ib>

²⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1ezhNo0al_RLu1_EC333iYd-GXPNa5ljsl4gsk7vvgj4/edit?usp=drive_link

²⁹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126>

Under the Consortium Agreement Mandate³⁰ the Form of Accession (new partners) may be found in the Appendices of the CA. If you feel a legal agreement is needed within the project, please contact STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org who will be able to advise.

5. PROJECT MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Figure 2. Governance structure.

5.1. Description of Project Roles and Responsibilities

In the following section, the roles of major stakeholders in the ELIXIR-STEERS project are described alongside the responsibilities, expectations, rights and duties of each participant in the project.

5.1.1. Project Coordinator

Name:	Andrew Smith
Organisation:	ELIXIR Hub

³⁰ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WH6aOvzrOOsmly5lUyKHWG7fx4yR2Ok0/view?usp=drive_link

Email:	andrew.smith@elixir-europe.org
Role:	<p>The ELIXIR Hub is appointed as Coordinator. The Coordinator shall act through a designated Representative, Andrew Smith.</p> <p>The Coordinator is and shall be a central point of contact between the Beneficiaries and the EC in particular regarding the management of the Grant.</p> <p>Specific duties: Legal signatory, legal responsibility for contract, budget oversight and control, submission of deliverables and milestones to EC, chair of GA and MB. The Coordinator is supported by the Project Management Team in regards to financial and contractual administration of the project.</p>

5.1.2. General Assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is composed of representatives of all project Beneficiaries that have delegated the decision making to the HoN. The GA will be informed of the project progress in a timely manner (Board meeting minutes circulated to all partners).

If necessary, each Beneficiary shall also be entitled to nominate a replacement Representative in the event that the original Representative is unable to attend any scheduled meetings of the General Assembly.

Meetings

The GA will meet face to face once a year with the Managing Board at the ELIXIR All Hands meeting to be updated on the project progress and plans.

A Representative of the Coordinator shall chair the General Assembly. The Chairperson of the General Assembly shall:

- be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the General Assembly; and
- chair meetings of the General Assembly.

Where the Chairperson of the General Assembly cannot attend a General Assembly meeting, the General Assembly shall nominate a replacement to chair the meeting for the purposes of such meeting of the General Assembly only, provided that the replacement must be a Representative. Such replacement shall be deemed Chairperson of the General Assembly.

Table 8. General Assembly members

Participant	GA member
EMBL	Andrew Smith

VIB	Frederik Coppens
CING	George Spyrou
UCY	Vasilis Promponas
UOCHB	Jiří Vondrášek
UFR	Björn Grüning
UTARTU	Hedi Peterson
BSC	Alfonso Valencia
CSC	Juha Törnroos
INRAE	Matéo Boudet
BSRCAF	Martin Reczko
ATHENA RC	Thanasis Vergoulis
HPI	Artemis Hatzigeorgiou
CERTH	Fotis Psomopoulos
UZSM	Fran Borovecki
HUN-REN TTK	Balázs Györffy
UCD	Colm Ryan
WEIZMANN	Dan Ben-Avraham
CNR	Marco Tangaro

UNIPD	Silvio Tosatto
PNED	Wei Gu
HEALTH-RI	Janet Vos
UiB	Sushma Grellschied
UiT	Erin Calhoun
biodata.pt	Ana de Freitas
UU	Bengt Persson
UL	Brane Leskošek
CSIC	Jose Maria Carazo Garcia
SDU	Veit Schwämmle
UCPH	Lars Juhl Jensen
SIB	Mark Ibberson
UNIMAN	Carole Goble
EARLHAM	Nicola Soranzo
UV	Thomas Rattei
CRB	Bogdan Mirauta

See Section 6.1 of the Consortium Agreement³¹ for further information regarding the General Assembly.

³¹ As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

5.1.3. Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN)

The Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN) is composed of the Heads of each ELIXIR Node and is chaired by the ELIXIR Director. The Heads of Nodes Committee is the senior scientific decision making body and management team within ELIXIR: together with the Director, the HoN Committee develops the ELIXIR Scientific Programme, decides on grant application strategies and oversees ELIXIR technical activities. The HoN Committee takes the leading role in developing the strategy for ELIXIR services, monitoring of performance as well as identification of service gaps.

As the senior scientific management team for ELIXIR, the HoN Committee will also maintain the overview of the technical and scientific activities in the infrastructure to ensure scientific excellence and impact. The Managing Board (see below) will update the HoN quarterly on the project progress and the HoN will be the decision making body for this project with one vote per Node.

The Heads of Nodes Committee (HoN) shall be responsible for the determination of policies and decision making in relation to the overall management of the Action and finding amicable solutions for any unresolved disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action.

Meetings

HoN meetings take place quarterly.

A Representative of the Coordinator shall chair the HoN meeting. The Chairperson of the HoN meeting shall:

- be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the HoN; and
- chair meetings of the HoN.

Where the Chairperson of the HoN cannot attend a HoN meeting, the HoN shall nominate a replacement to chair the meeting for the purposes of such a meeting of the HoN only, provided that the replacement must be a Representative. Such replacement shall be deemed Chairperson of the HoN.

The Heads of Nodes Committee meets at least every twelve (12) months at venues to be agreed, or at any other time at the request of any of the Beneficiaries. Such other meetings may be held via face-to-face or telephone or video conference allowing votes to be submitted verbally.

See Section 6.1 of the Consortium Agreement³² for further information regarding the Heads of Nodes.

Table 9. Heads of Nodes (HoN) Committee

³² As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

Node	HoN	Deputy
Belgium	Dr Frederik Coppens	Dr Kim De Ruyck
Czech Republic	Dr Jiří Vondrášek	Dr Karel Berka
Denmark	Prof. Jan Gorodkin	n/a
EMBL-EBI	Dr Johanna McEntyre and Dr Ewan Birney	TBC
Estonia	Prof. Hedi Peterson	Dr Kairi Koort
Finland	Dr Tommi Nyrönen	Dr Ilkka Lappalainen and Dr Susanna Repo
France	Prof. Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon and Dr Guy Perrière	n/a
Germany	Prof. Oliver Kohlbacher and Prof. Alexander Sczyrba	Dr Irena Maus
Greece	Dr Martin Reczko	Dr Christoforos Nikolaou
Hungary	Dr Balázs Györfy	n/a
Ireland	Prof. Denis Shields	Dr Colm Ryan
Israel	Dr Dan Ben-Avraham	n/a
Italy	Prof. Graziano Pesole	Prof. Silvio Tosatto and Dr Francesca De Leo
Luxembourg	Dr Reinhard Schneider	Dr Wei Gu
Netherlands	Prof. Jaap Heringa	Prof. Chris Evelo
Norway	Dr Sushma Nagaraja Grellscheid	Prof. Eivind Hovig
Portugal	Prof. Ana Teresa Freitas	Dr Inês Chaves
Slovenia	Dr Barbara Koroušič Seljak	n/a
Spain	Prof. Alfonso Valencia	Dr Salvador Capella-Gutierrez
Sweden	Prof. Bengt Persson	Dr Jessica Lindvall
Switzerland	Dr Christophe Dessimoz	n/a
UK	Prof. Carole Goble and Prof. Neil Hall	n/a
Croatia (prospective member)	Prof. Fran Borovečki	n/a

Cyprus (prospective member)	Dr George Spyrou	Dr Vasilis Promponas
Romania (prospective member)	Prof. Marius Mihășan	n/a
Austria (observer)	Prof. Thomas Rattei	n/a

5.1.4. Work Package Leaders

The Work Package Leads (WPLs) are responsible for overseeing the technical progress of the project and ensure interoperability and alignment of co-dependent tasks across work packages. They are also responsible for presenting the work carried out by the WP to the European Commission and for the content of their WP activities within the periodic reports.

WPLs are responsible for the proper execution of the DoA and the implementation of the decisions of the HoN and Managing Board. The Work Package Leaders collectively make up the Managing Board. They are expected to identify issues, risks and opportunities within the technical tasks of the Project and take appropriate actions to ensure the project delivers the anticipated benefits both at work package and project level. Risks or opportunities that cut across more than one work package should, together with a suggested action, be elevated to the Managing Board during the monthly meetings. The WPLs, as the Managing Board and via the Coordinator, report on the project progress to the HoNs at least every 6 months.

WPLs are responsible for filtering project information from the Managing Board meetings to their work packages via their dedicated WP distribution lists, during their regular meetings, or via other communication means they deem fit, e.g. Slack. WPLs are responsible for scheduling their own WP meetings, creating and circulating an agenda, and taking and disseminating minutes.

In case of Beneficiaries not performing their roles, WPLs are expected to promptly document the situation and raise it with the PMT in order to swiftly address reputational or technical risk for the consortium.

Where a WPL is unable to host one of their Work Package meetings or attend a Managing Board meeting they may deputise to their predefined Deputy Work Package Leader.

Contact: STEERS-wpls@elixir-europe.org

For more information, please refer to the ELIXIR Hub document Work Package Leader's Good Practice Guide³³.

³³https://docs.google.com/document/d/1jZAhcO4wYMsm8pdd22vO7wNai0wg83H7Fm_R08EL_FO/edit#heading=h.d7m9lv9j5el8

5.1.5. Managing Board

The Managing Board (MB) is composed of the Project Coordinator and the Work Package Leaders and is responsible for ensuring alignment and coordination across Work Packages and for the successful execution of the project.

The Managing Board shall be responsible for the overall execution of the Action, the quality of the Action, alignment across all Work Packages, decision making and the initial finding of amicable solutions for any disputes between the Beneficiaries relating to the execution of the Action. The MB will ensure the smooth operation of the Action and guarantee that all efforts are focused towards the Action Objectives, Deliverables and Milestones. This will be achieved by regular meetings, at least every month, and thorough reviews of progress reports. It will also ensure that all Beneficiaries are regularly updated on the scientific progress. The responsibilities are fully detailed in the ELIXIR-STEERS Consortium Agreement³⁴.

MB members shall have named deputies to ensure proper representation in all meetings.

The Managing Board will be supported by the Project Management Team (PMT).

Meetings

The Managing Board will meet at least every month. In addition to the monthly teleconferences, the MB shall meet twice a year face to face making use of regular ELIXIR events such as the ELIXIR All Hands and HoN face to face meetings.

A Representative of the Project Coordinator will act as the chairperson of the Managing Board (the "Chairperson of the Managing Board") and shall:

- a) with assistance from the Project Management Team, be responsible for the convening of meetings, preparation and distribution of the agenda and minutes for meetings of the Managing Board; and
- b) chair meetings of the Managing Board.

Where a Work Package Leader is unable to attend a meeting they may send their predefined Deputy Work Package Leader.

See Section 6.1 of the Consortium Agreement³⁵ for further information regarding the Managing Board.

Table 10. Managing Board members

Role	Managing Board Member	Managing Board Deputy
Project Coordinator	Andrew Smith (ELIXIR Hub)	

³⁴ As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

³⁵ As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

WP1 Leader	Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub), Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub)	
WP2 Leader	Silvio Tosatto (UNIPD), John Hancock (UL), Fotis Psomopoulos (CERTH)	Federica Quaglia (UNIPD)
WP3 Leader	Frederik Coppens (VIB), Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (BSC)	Rafael Buono (VIB), Laura Portell (BSC)
WP4 Leader	Jessica Lindvall (UU), Jiří Vondrašek (UOCHB), Ana de Freitas (biodata.pt)	Mariana De Freitas (biodata.pt)
WP5 Leader	Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub), Despoina Sousoni (ELIXIR Hub), Joana Wingender (ELIXIR Hub)	

Contact: STEERS-wpls@elixir-europe.org

5.1.6. SAB (Scientific Advisory Board)

ELIXIR-STEERS will make use of ELIXIR's Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) for progress review. The ELIXIR SAB regularly review the ELIXIR Nodes and will provide recommendations for the scientific strategy of this project in the context of overall ELIXIR Strategy as well as individual Node strategies. The ELIXIR SAB includes experts in the biological and biomedical life science area whose backgrounds cover science and industry and are elected by the ELIXIR Board.

Meetings

The SAB meet in person once a year, usually in February and hold one summer Teleconference, in June. They provide direct feedback to the ELIXIR Board and the Director on relevant ELIXIR activities. The ELIXIR SAB will meet with the ELIXIR Director and Managing Board representatives face-to-face yearly at the ELIXIR SAB F2F meeting.

See Section 6.1 of the Consortium Agreement³⁶ for further information regarding the SAB.

Table 11. SAB members

SAB member	Affiliation
Prof. Philip Bourne (Vice-Chair)	University of Virginia, USA
Prof. Fiona Brinkman	Simon Fraser University, Canada
Prof. Melissa Haendel	University of Colorado Anschutz Medical Campus, USA

³⁶ As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

Dr Janet Kelso	Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology, Germany
Dr Danielle Kemmer	Novo Nordisk Foundation, Denmark
Dr Paul Kersey	Kew Gardens, UK
Prof. Bartha Maria Knoppers	McGill University, Canada
Dr Eric Meslin	University of Toronto, Canada
Prof. Nicola Mulder	UCT Computational Biology Group, South Africa
Dr BF Francis Ouellette	Bioinformatics.ca, Canada
Dr Augusto Rendon	Genomics England, UK
Dr Doreen Ware (Chair)	USDA ARS, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, USA

Contact: sab@elixir-europe.org

5.1.7. Ethics Advisor

In addition to the SAB, ELIXIR-STEERS will appoint to the project an independent, external Ethics Advisor with specific experience in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the ethics issues around its use. This individual may also be considered for the role on the ELIXIR SAB. The appointment process will be as follows:

- Call for recommendations/nominations for the Ethics Advisor role, from the ELIXIR-STEERS Managing Board (MB), was collected by the Coordinator (deadline 22/03/2024)
- Research was then conducted into each nominated candidate to:
 - Confirm whether any conflict of interest exists (e.g. that the person is already a part of or has links to the ELIXIR-STEERS Consortium).
 - Evaluate the expertise and background of each nominee (including locality, with a preference for EU-based).
- Once information had been collated, a short list of candidates was reviewed by the ELIXIR-STEERS Managing Board (April 2024)
- Prospective candidates were then individually contacted by the STEERS Coordination Team, in order of preference as decided by the MB, to explain the requirements and ascertain whether they would be interested in taking on the role.
- Heidi Beate Bentzen was appointed as Ethics Advisor to the project in December 2024.

The AI Ethics Advisor, with the support of the project coordinator, will:

- Attend the General Assembly meetings of the project and any others if mutually deemed essential
- Produce the annual ethics reports (two in total)
- If required, attend the periodic project review meeting or the MB meetings to present and discuss their report.

5.1.8 IAC (Industry Advisory Committee)

The ELIXIR Industry Advisory Committee (IAC) provides the ELIXIR Director and HoN with high-level strategic advice on industry needs and opportunities within the ELIXIR programme to promote open innovation and public-private research partnership. The IAC comprises experts from the bioinformatics industry, including SMEs and large multinational companies (appointed by ELIXIR Board).

Meetings

The IAC meets face to face once per year. The ELIXIR IAC will meet with the ELIXIR Director and MB representatives face to face (collocated with the ELIXIR SAB F2F meeting) and via TC as and when required.

See Clause 11.7 of the Consortium Agreement³⁷ for further information regarding the IAC.

Table 12. IAC members

Name	Affiliation
Ian Barrett	AstraZeneca, UK
Thomas Exner	Seven Past Nine GmbH, Germany
Richard Finkers	GenNovation B.V., the Netherlands
Andreas Kremer	ITTM, Luxembourg
Klaus Maisinger	Illumina, UK
Geert de Meyer	Waltham Petcare Science Institute, MARS UK, UK
Filip Pattyn (Vice-Chair)	FAQIR, Belgium
Jörg Peplies	Ribocon GmbH, Germany
Elizabeth Reynolds	General Bioinformatics, UK
Helena Saunders	Syngenta, UK

³⁷ As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

Catherine Sirven	Bayer, France
Bérénice Wulbrecht	ONTOFORCE, Belgium

Contact: iac@elixir-europe.org

5.1.9. Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team (PMT) will be led by the ELIXIR Project Management Office and leverage their experience and processes for managing large, international consortia to ensure timely delivery and effective communication and collaboration across WPs, and towards internal and external stakeholders.

Table 13. Project Management Team (PMT)

Name:	Mado Fernandez / Juan Arenas
Organisation:	ELIXIR Hub
Email:	steers-coordination@elixir-europe.org
Role:	<p>The PMT assists the Managing Board. It is responsible for the day-to-day execution of the Project, providing the necessary project management support to deliver the Project.</p> <p>In particular, the PMT is responsible for the following tasks and activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● implementation of all management and organisational tasks ● scheduling of decisions ● monitoring the achievement of set milestones ● timely submission of deliverables ● organisation and documentation of the meetings of the Consortium Bodies ● dissemination of all relevant information and action items across the Consortium ● accounting for all financial aspects of the Project and ensuring timely submission of all required reports to the EC.

The PM Team will support and report on the execution of the project work plan and budget utilisation, providing the mechanism to identify and manage project risks and opportunities.

A consortium communication strategy will be established (WP5) making appropriate use of digital resources. Communication dynamics will be promoted across the project, keeping the right level

of engagement among stakeholders. Specific collaboration tools will be enabled from the first stages of the Project. These tools will guarantee the means for efficient communication within the Consortium fulfilling internal communication needs, and external stakeholders needs (WP5).

Meetings

The PM Team meet on a weekly basis.

5.1.10. Task Leaders

Each Work Package is broken down into tasks and sub-tasks.

Each Task Lead is responsible for prompt and on time performance and fulfilment of the assigned task and subtask as per the Description of Action (DoA) in cooperation with all task participants and liaising with the respective WPL.

The Task Leads must ensure that the fulfilment of their task activities are accomplished in due time in line with the commitments identified in the DoA.

Task Leads shall promptly notify the WPL of any significant problem or delay likely to affect the completion of the assigned task.

Each participant must ensure timely contribution to the allocated tasks, as requested by each Task Leads and/or WPLs. Any encountered issue should be discussed with the Task Lead and, if needed, escalated to the WPL level.

The designated Task Leaders are presented in Table 14 below.

Table 14. Task Leaders

Task #	Task Leader	Email	Organisation
T1.1	Mado Fernandez / Juan Arenas	mado.fernandez@elixir-europe.org / juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T1.2	Mado Fernandez / Juan Arenas	mado.fernandez@elixir-europe.org / juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T1.3	Mado Fernandez / Juan Arenas	mado.fernandez@elixir-europe.org / juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T1.4	Mado Fernandez / Juan Arenas	mado.fernandez@elixir-europe.org / juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T1.5	Ivana Versic / Jilly Cheshire / Mado Fernandez	ivana.versic@elixir-europe.org / jilly.cheshire@elixir-europe.org / mado.fernandez@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub

T2.1	Silvio Tosatto	silvio.tosatto@unipd.it	UNIPD
T2.2	Fotis Psomopoulos	fpsom@certh.gr	CERTH
T2.3	John Hancock	johnmichael.hancock@mf.uni-lj.si	UL
T3.1	Thanasis Vergoulis	vergoulis@athenarc.gr	ATHENA RC
T3.2	Marek Suchánek / Jan Slifka	marek.suchanek@uochb.cas.cz / slifka@uochb.cas.cz	UOCHB
T3.3	Laura Portell Silva / Salvador Capella-Gutierrez	laura.portell@bsc.es / salvador.capella@bsc.es	BSC
T3.4	Nicola Soranzo	nicola.soranzo@earlham.ac.uk	EARLHAM
T4.1	David Dolan	David.Dolan@uib.no	UiB
T4.2	Mariana De Freitas	marianadefreitas@biodata.pt	biodata.pt
T4.3	Erin Calhoun	erin.calhoun@uit.no	UiT
T5.1	Elaine Harrison	elaine.harrison@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T5.2	Despoina Sousoni	despoina.sousoni@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T5.3	Erika Balsyte	erika.balsyte@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub
T5.4	Andrea Guzman Mesa	andrea.guzmanmesa@elixir-europe.org	ELIXIR Hub

The most up-to-date Task Leader list is available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive³⁸.

5.1.11. Deliverable Authors

The following Deliverable Lead Authors are responsible for the production of the deliverables according to the deliverable preparation procedure defined in Section 7.1 (Deliverables).

Table 15. Deliverable Lead Authors

Deliverab	Deliverable title	Name of Lead Author	Organisati
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³⁸ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18vTAvllOdes6Vz3LznX0E28dJsWMxMPv>

le #			on
D1.1	Project Handbook	Nikki Coutts	ELIXIR Hub
D1.2	Data Management Plan (DMP)	Nikki Coutts	ELIXIR Hub
D1.3	Updated Project Handbook - V2	Nikki Coutts	ELIXIR Hub
D1.4	Updated Data Management Plan (DMP) - V2	Juan Arenas	ELIXIR Hub
D1.5	ELIXIR Gender Equality Strategy	Ivana Versic	ELIXIR Hub
D1.6	Updated Project Handbook - V3	Mado Fernandez	ELIXIR Hub
D1.7	Project Long-Term Sustainability Plan		EMBL
D1.8	Updated Data Management Plan (DMP) -V3	Juan Arenas	ELIXIR Hub
D1.9	ELIXIR-STEERS Policy Briefing	Andrea Guzman Mesa	ELIXIR Hub
D1.10	Updated ELIXIR-STEERS Policy Briefing	Andrea Guzman Mesa	ELIXIR Hub
D2.1	Report on best-practices and indicators available and used by selected Communities	John Hancock	UL
D2.2	Research software and workflows best-practice toolkit	Silvio Tosatto	UNIPD
D3.1	Report on credit and software management plan implementation	Thanasis Vergoulis	ATHENA RC
D3.2	Report on Community-led efforts to identify critical components across workflows	Frederik Coppens	VIB
D4.1	Customised programme on the implementation of training skills for research infrastructure	Jiří Vondrašek	UL
D4.2	ELIXIR Node Development Almanack	Erin Calhoun	UiB
D4.3	Deposit of ELITMa new training materials in an open access repository and register in TeSS	Ana Freitas	biodata.pt

D5.1	Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation, including Project Communications Plan	Elaine Harrison	ELIXIR Hub
D5.2	Report showcasing industry engagement success stories	Despoina Sousoni	ELIXIR Hub
D6.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1: Ethics Advisor_Emerging issues of AI need to be monitored - SENSITIVE	Nikki Coutts / External Ethics Advisor	ELIXIR Hub
D6.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2: A report prepared by the external independent advisor must be submitted as a deliverable at the end of each reporting period - SENSITIVE	Mado Fernandez / External Ethics Advisor	ELIXIR Hub
D6.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3: A report prepared by the external independent advisor must be submitted as a deliverable at the end of each reporting period - SENSITIVE	Mado Fernandez / External Ethics Advisor	ELIXIR Hub

The most up-to-date list of Deliverable Authors list is available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive³⁹.

5.2 How and when the project bodies meet

The Coordinator, supported by the PM Team, is responsible for convening meetings of the management and governance bodies at the STEERS overall level (i.e. GA, MB, SAB), complying with the minimum frequency of ordinary meetings as defined in the STEERS Consortium Agreement (CA) and detailed above. Work Package Leaders have the responsibility of calling meetings within their respective WPs as needed.

According to the CA, the bodies of the STEERS governance will have at least the following meeting frequency:

Table 16. Meeting Frequency

Meeting Frequency	Project Bodies
Weekly	PM (TC)

³⁹ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18vTAvllQdes6Vz3LznX0E28dJsWMxMPv>

Monthly	MB (TC)
Bi-Annually	MB (F2F), SAB (F2F & TC)
Annually	GA (F2F), HoN (F2F), IAC (F2F)
As needed	HoN (TC or F2F), IAC (TC)

Organisation of meetings comprises the following tasks:

- professional convocation and on time distribution of the agenda according to the terms of the Grant Agreement;
- organisation of facilities or conference venues with the required infrastructure and catering, to ensure the smooth running of the conference (when face-to-face);
- organisation and steering of decision-making processes at STEERS meetings
- distribution of minutes following the meeting and follow-up of points agreed at the meetings.

5.3. Beneficiaries

5.3.1. How Beneficiaries change their representatives to the General Assembly (GA)

Beneficiaries' representatives in the General Assembly (GA) are expected to be maintained throughout the project. Any representative in the GA may nominate a substitute to attend and vote at any meeting. In that respect, any change in a representative in the GA must be informed by the original representative, in writing (including electronic mail), to the Chair (Coordinator) at least one week before an ordinary meeting of the GA takes place, indicating the reason for substitution and identifying the new representative.

GA members can be accompanied by other representatives of their respective institutions at meetings, but only one vote per institution is allowed in the GA.

5.3.2. What are the main Beneficiaries' responsibilities?

Beneficiaries must use all reasonable endeavours to perform and fulfil, promptly, and on time, all of their obligations under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, to accomplish the purpose and objectives of the STEERS project and act in cooperation and mutual trust. Beneficiaries shall also provide their respective contributions to deliverables, information, and reports as required by the WPLs, the MB, the PM Team, and the Coordinator, so as to help these bodies to fulfil their obligations.

Beneficiaries shall promptly notify the Coordinator and the PM Team through the appropriate WPL of any significant problem or delay likely to affect the success of the project.

To summarise, each Beneficiary must:

- Do the work assigned to it in the Description of Action, and any other detailed work plan derived from it, on time, on budget, and with an appropriate level of quality.
- Collaborate with all other Beneficiaries as required by the tasks, including contributing to relevant deliverables.
- Not hinder the work of others or delay it unnecessarily.
- Attend meetings and teleconferences as required.
- Notify promptly the relevant governance body of any potential issue affecting performance. The normal chain of reporting would be, in this order: WPL → PM → MB.
- Notify the PM Team about any risk that may be detected in the course of the work, and that may affect future performance.
- Fulfil the administrative and financial reporting obligations according to EC rules.
- Spend the costs foreseen only for the work expected in STEERS, and report it faithfully.

6. KEY LEGAL DOCUMENTS

6.1. The Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement (GA) is the main legal document underpinning the project's execution – effectively, a contract between the Beneficiaries and the EC. It is first signed by the EC and the Coordinator. Each Beneficiary then accedes to the Grant Agreement by executing an accession form. The Grant Agreement mainly provides information on the grant (parties, duration, start date, budget, etc.), obligations of the Beneficiaries towards the EC (such as reporting requirements), as well as the intellectual property framework and other legal conditions. The Grant Agreement is dated 1st February 2024 and has the GA # 101131096.

The Grant Agreement core document includes a standard text (i.e. it is essentially the same for any EC Horizon Europe project) describing the general rules and regulations governing EC projects, including financial rules (e.g. which costs are acceptable, how payments are handled, etc.), Intellectual Property Rights (who owns the results, how access to such results is enabled, etc.) and other general conditions applicable to EC projects. These generic provisions can be supplemented (but not contravened) with project-specific provisions via a Consortium Agreement (see below), which enables projects to set out their specific IPR detailed rules, governance mechanisms, etc.

Beyond its core terms and conditions, mostly standard text, the Grant Agreement also includes the following annexes, which form an integral part of the contract:

6.1.1. Annex 1. Description of the action (DoA)

The most extensive and important Annex to the Grant Agreement is the Description of Action (DoA), which comprises the technical description of the work to be undertaken in the project (work packages, tasks, deliverables, milestones), the description and roles of the different partners, allocated effort in person-months, and budget details. The DoA is derived from the original proposal submitted to the EC for evaluation and approval, and it is the benchmark against

which project progress will be judged. Compared to the rest of the Grant Agreement and annexes, which are mostly model texts, the DoA is specific for each project. It is important to remember that the DoA is an integral part of the Grant Agreement, and therefore it is a contractual commitment of all Beneficiaries.

6.1.2. Annex 2. Estimated Budget for the action

This Annex refers to the overall budget for the STEERS Project and includes the budget details for all project Beneficiaries. This document is automatically generated by the EC Participant Portal.

6.1.3. Annex 3. Accession form for Beneficiaries

This form is required to be signed by all the project Beneficiaries to formally accede to the STEERS Grant Agreement. If a new Beneficiary joins the project, this form will be requested to be signed by the new institution joining the project.

6.1.4. Annex 4. Financial statement

This form refers to the summary of costs to be reported by those partners receiving EC funding for each reporting period. Please see section 7.3.3. (Financial Reporting) for more details.

6.1.5. Annex 5. Model for the Certificate on Financial Statements

This Annex is required for those partners that request a total EC funding of €430,000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs calculated based on its usual cost accounting practices. Please see section 7.3.3. (Financial Reporting) for more details.

6.1.6. Annex 6. Model for the Certificate on the Methodology

Beneficiaries may submit to the EC, for approval by the Commission, a certificate on the methodology to state that their usual cost accounting practices comply with specific conditions (e.g. "unit costs" instead of actual costs). Once the certificate is approved, costs declared in line with this methodology will not be challenged subsequently, unless the Beneficiaries have concealed information for the purpose of the approval.

The Grant Agreement and its Annexes are available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁴⁰.

6.1.7. Changes to the Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement can and must be changed whenever any important project parameter changes: partnership, project duration, budget, etc. Implementation of such changes must follow a specific procedure called 'Grant Agreement amendment'. Most changes that trigger Grant Agreement amendments relate to updates in the Description of Action (DoA) (e.g. changes in tasks and deliverables, changes in efforts allocated, changes in partner's teams, budget transfers across Beneficiaries, etc.). These can be relatively minor, in which case they tend to be grouped and implemented together in one go, or major, which might trigger an amendment on their own, especially if it is urgent that the change is officially entered into the contract.

⁴⁰ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18vTAvllOdes6Vz3LznX0E28dJsWMxMPv>

Grant Agreement amendments are submitted to the EC by the Coordinator on behalf of the Consortium. This implies that the Consortium must be aware of and approve any proposed changes before the amendment is requested.

The PM Team will be responsible for following-up on amendments to the Grant Agreement during the project.

The procedure is as follows:

1. The Project Management Team (PM Team) will keep track of all needed amendments. Meetings and communications with the Beneficiaries affected will enable the PM Team to compile all the necessary information to support the changes.
2. The list of changes will be presented to the MB for initial approval.
3. The list of modifications will then be circulated to the General Assembly for their information and approval.
4. The PM Team will prepare the following documentation:
 - A new version of the DoA with the modifications in track changes.
 - A first version of a "Request Letter" to be sent to the EC Project Officer including the changes.
 - Other documents needed to request modifications.
5. The PM Team will circulate an amended version of the DoA to the Managing Board for validation. The approval by the Managing Board will be required for any Amendment to the Grant Agreement.
6. As a final step the Coordinator, supported by the PM Team, will submit on behalf of the Consortium, the Request Letter, the new version of the DoA and all the additional documentation required by EC for the changes submitted.
7. Once approved, the new version of the DoA will also be accessible in the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁴¹ in the appropriate amendment folder.

The Grant Agreement may be affected by other types of minor changes which do not constitute an amendment, but which must be communicated to the consortium or to the EC through an information procedure. In any case, Beneficiaries should contact the PM Team to confirm the procedure to follow for any modification needed.

For more information about the procedure, review the section 4.3. (Project Change Management).

6.2. The Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement (CA) is concluded between the STEERS Beneficiaries in order to provide a legal framework for their collaboration within the boundaries of the Grant Agreement.

⁴¹ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1fitg1EO8rylRGM7tBYCaCrB6OSGtjly>

The CA includes provisions on, for instance, governance, intellectual property, dissemination, and liability. The EC is not a party to the CA. Once fully executed the CA will be accessible in the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁴².

Amendments to the CA may also be necessary in the course of the project, sometimes purely as a consequence of Grant Agreement amendments. These CA amendments will be handled separately by agreement of all Beneficiaries, under the coordination of the Coordinator with the support of the PM Team.

The Project Coordinator shall keep records of the Consortium Agreement together with (i) all amendments to the Grant Agreement amending the Consortium Agreement, and (ii) any other amendments to the Consortium Agreement.

7. PROJECT REPORTING

7.1. Deliverables

7.1.1. Who generates project deliverables?

As official results of the project, deliverables deserve special attention and are generated and reviewed according to specific procedures. As a general rule, the generation of deliverables is a responsibility of the corresponding Work Package lead Beneficiary and the process will be supervised by the corresponding WPL. The lead Beneficiary will be responsible for drafting the deliverable and gathering contributions from Work Package participants as appropriate. Prior to submission to the EC, deliverables will undergo an internal review process that is detailed below.

In order to ensure uniformity in the presentation across the project and facilitate the consolidation of contributions from different partners, the template for deliverables has been generated by the PM Team based on the official EC template, and it is available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive in the Guidance and Templates folder⁴³. Please note that an individual template has been created for each Deliverable within the relevant WP's 'Working documents' folder (links to these can also be found in the 'Commitments' tab of the Project Monitoring spreadsheet).

When naming the document it is expected that the document naming convention is adhered to.

Example: ELIXIR-STEERS_Del#_Title_Version#.

(e.g. ELIXIR-STEERS_D5.3_Project Handbook_v1.0.pdf)

7.1.2. Deliverable structure, guidance and tips

Project deliverables are to be submitted at specific times stated in the DoA (Part A - List of deliverables, p.21/22⁴⁴).

⁴² https://drive.google.com/file/d/1WH6aOvzrQOsmly5IUyKHWG7fx4yR2Qk0/view?usp=drive_link

⁴³ https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1uH4JirHcQ07aw1YSMydS4Ek6yBdthl_x

⁴⁴ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1M3aVr61IUfOoP6hr83gvt6fpTevvdcYW>

Note: The “expected delivery date” listed in the DoA always refers to the last date of any month. e.g. ‘June 2024’ means ‘30th June 2024’ / ‘Feb 2024’ means ‘28th Feb 2024’.

Deliverables reflect the results achieved during the lifetime of the project, and they are important documents to assess the progress achieved.

Each deliverable must use the deliverable template pre-prepared by the PM Team and shared in the Project Monitoring spreadsheet (‘Commitments’ tab)⁴⁵. In addition, a clean copy of the deliverable template can be found in the Templates folder on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁴⁶.

The template has the following predefined sections:

- Executive Summary (Max ½ page, should provide an overview of the work carried out and the conclusion)
- Contribution Towards Project Objectives (indicate with Yes/No if the deliverable contributes to the key result)
- Introduction (1-1 ½ pages, describe deliverable scope and the methodology to be applied)
- Description of Work Accomplished (Describe what has been done. Interactions with other WPs? Collaboration with external partners/projects? Dissemination activities carried out?)
- Results (Present and discuss the results obtained)
- Conclusion
- Impact (Present and discuss the impact obtained)
- Next Steps
- Deviation from Description of Action (If applicable, describe the deviation from the Description of Action and the justification and plans to avoid this deviation impacting the work plan)

7.1.3. Deliverable review process

7.1.3.1. Review for quality

The review process must use the following quality criteria as reference.

As regards to content:

- **Completeness:** Information must address all aspects related to the purpose for which the information is produced. On the other hand, redundancy of information must be avoided, as it obscures the clarity of documents.

Related indicators: Missing content, Redundancy.

- **Accuracy:** Information contained in the document must be reliable and must correspond with reality. This means that all background information used in the reports should be

⁴⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6InrFQW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126>

⁴⁶ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/19-rq9NSjHjCpU5MLsCKMUeUZz7wf35Ib>

appropriately supported by references. Foreground information should be sufficiently supported so that misinterpretation is avoided. Use of statistically validated objective data is to be prioritised.

Related indicators: Error, Insufficient references/objective supporting data, Ambiguity.

- Relevance: Information used in the document should be focused on the key issues and be written in a fashion that takes into consideration its target audience.

Related indicators: Irrelevant information.

- Depth: all information used should be provided to the depth needed for the purpose of the document.

Related indicators: Lacking detail, Excessive detail.

As regards to appearance and structure:

- Adherence to standards: it is important that deliverables are prepared with uniform appearance and structure so that, even if they are produced by different authors, they appear as originating from a single initiative.

Related indicators: Lack of uniformity in presentation.

7.1.3.2. The review process

Within the STEERS project, the review process shall be coordinated by the PM Team.

As and when a deliverable approaches due, the PM Team will contact the named lead Beneficiary and the relevant WPL. A link to the deliverable template will be provided, as well as guidelines for producing the document.

If the WPL themselves will not be drafting the deliverable, it is their responsibility to forward the request to the appropriate team member(s) who will be undertaking the task of drafting the deliverable (the deliverable authors).

The Deliverable Lead must nominate a minimum of two reviewers. Before informing the PM Team of who the reviewers will be they should seek agreement from the nominated reviewers. The reviewers should ideally be from a different WP and have a thorough understanding of the deliverable topic so they can provide sufficient technical critique/review. If it is deemed that the review by someone with additional expertise is required, e.g. such as a case where a deliverable has a focus on ethical or regulatory/legal issues, members of any of the Advisory Boards of the STEERS project may also be asked to be a reviewer.

The deliverable author(s) should work on their deliverable within their Work Package folder on the STEERS Google Shared Drive.

Where more than one person is producing the deliverable, the lead deliverable author should create a Table of Contents and assign responsibilities to the other authors.

If the WPL(s) do not draft the report themselves, once the first draft of the document is produced by the author(s), they will be expected to have the WPLs review it to assess the content from a scientific/technical perspective.

Reviewers will be expected to check the deliverable against the quality criteria described in section 4.4.2. above. Any suggested edits or comments should be made within the Google Doc which allows for a collaborative working environment. The deliverable author(s), must then proceed with the amendments or comments on the reviewed document.

1.5 weeks prior to the deliverable due date, the final draft of the document should be submitted to the PM Team, by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the STEERS Google Shared Drive. PM will distribute the link to the MB for a final review, allowing the MB seven (7) days to review it. Once approved, the PM Team (on behalf of the Project Coordinator) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and submit the final document to the EC via the Participant Portal. In addition, the PM Team will upload all public deliverable reports to Zenodo (see also Section 4.6.5, Open Access policy and requirements) and notify the Consortium. The final document will also be available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive in the Deliverables and Milestones folder⁴⁷.

During the whole process, it is recommended that there is one responsible author that acts on behalf of all authors and communicates with them for evolving the document.

7.1.3.3. Illustrative timelines

1. **Three months** prior to the due date, the deliverable will appear in the project monitoring dashboard with a link to the pre-prepared deliverable template.
2. **Two months (60 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) identify the reviewers and inform PM.
3. If multiple people will be producing the deliverable, the lead author should create a Table of Contents and assign responsibilities to the other authors.
4. Author(s) produce the first draft of the deliverable report.
5. If the author(s) are not the WPLs, they must have the WPLs review the deliverable report.
6. **1 month (30 days)** prior to the due date, the author(s) must send the draft report to the PM Team by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the STEERS Google Shared Drive. The PM Team will review the draft for formatting before forwarding it to the pre-identified reviewers, allowing them two weeks to provide comments directly within the Google Doc.
7. Reviewers' input is gathered within the Google Doc using suggested edits and comments.

⁴⁷ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1n2SEbtwmfhCxlyrLKSZrMIZftVN8KDWa>

8. Author(s) generate a revised version of the document taking on board the suggestions and comments of the reviewers.
9. **1.5 weeks (10 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) must send the final version to the PM Team by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the STEERS Google Shared Drive. PM Team will then circulate the document (via emailed link) to the MB (all WPLs) for final review, allowing them seven (7) days to review the document. The MB are encouraged to make any suggestions or comments directly within the Google Doc.
10. **Three days** prior to the due date, the author(s) provide the PM Team with the consolidated, final version.
11. The Coordinator (or the PM Team on their behalf) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and upload the final version in the Participant Portal and to Zenodo.
12. The final version of the document is also uploaded to the 'Submitted' folder within the respective reporting period subfolder (e.g. RP₁, RP₂, RP₃) in the 04. Deliverables and Milestones folder⁴⁸ on the STEERS Google Shared Drive.
04. Deliverables and Milestones → RP₁ → Uploaded documents

Note: Although the illustrative timeline starts three months prior to the due date with drafting beginning two months prior to the due date, this process can begin earlier if the authors wish, and deliverables can be submitted ahead of schedule.

In case of time constraints, an exceptional streamlined procedure for the deliverables may apply upon agreement with the MB.

The 'Commitments' tab of the Project Monitoring spreadsheet⁴⁹ listing all the deliverable due dates is available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁵⁰.

7.2. Milestones

Each milestone must use the milestone template and must not exceed one slide. For each milestone, a template has been pre-prepared by the PM Team and shared in the Project Monitoring spreadsheet ('Commitments' tab)⁵¹. In addition, a clean copy of the milestone template can be found in the Templates folder on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁵².

It is the responsibility of the Milestone Lead organisation⁵³ to produce the milestone report or to deputise the responsibility to someone else upon their agreement.

7.2.1. Illustrative timelines

1. **3 months** prior to the due date, the milestone will appear in the monthly project monitoring report with a link to the pre-prepared milestone template

⁴⁸ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1n2SEbtwmfhCxlyrLKSZrMIZftVN8KDWa>

⁴⁹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6InrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126>

⁵⁰ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18vTAyIIQdes6Vz3LznX0E28dJsWMxMPv>

⁵¹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6InrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126>

⁵² <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/19-rq9NSjHjCpU5MLsCKMUeUzZ7wf35Ib>

⁵³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlaWZeg3jbiqerFIFABmD5VQM6InrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126>

2. **1.5 months (45 days)** prior to the due date, if the author(s) are not the WPLs, they must have the WPLs review the milestone before submitting it.
3. **1.5 weeks (10 days)** prior to the due date, author(s) must send the final version to the PM Team by emailing them a link to the Google Doc version on the STEERS Google Shared Drive. PM will then circulate the document (via emailed link) to the MB (all WPLs) for final review, allowing them seven (7) days to provide any comment. The MB are encouraged to make any suggestions or comments directly within the Google Doc however, this shouldn't be a time consuming process for the MB.
4. **Three days** prior to the due date, the author(s) provide the PM Team with the final version.
5. The Coordinator (or the PM Team on their behalf) will convert the Google Doc to PDF and upload it in Participant Portal.
6. The final version of the document is also uploaded to the 'Uploaded documents' folder within the respective reporting period subfolder (e.g. RP₁, RP₂, RP₃) in the 04. Deliverables and Milestones folder⁵⁴ on the STEERS Google Shared Drive.

The 'Commitments' tab of the Project Monitoring spreadsheet⁵⁵ listing all the milestone due dates is available on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁵⁶.

7.3. Progress reporting

7.3.1. EC Project Periodic Technical Reports

Throughout the entire project execution period (1st February 2024 until 31st January 2027), the Consortium is required to submit, in due time, two periodic technical reports to the EC using the template periodic report⁵⁷ provided in the EC Participant Portal⁵⁸. The project is officially divided into 2 periods for both progress and financial reporting to the EC:

- RP1: 1st Feb 2024 to 31st July 2025 (M1-18)
- RP2: 1st August 2025 to 31st January 2027 (M19-36)

In compliance with the rules specified in Clause 4.2 of the STEERS Grant Agreement (Reporting and payment schedule)⁵⁹, periodic reports have to be submitted to the EC within 60 days after the end of each reporting period.

The periodic technical report must include the following:

- an explanation of the work carried out by the Beneficiaries;

⁵⁴ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1n2SEbtwmfhCxlyrLKSZrMIZftVN8KDWa>

⁵⁵ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/14XhjdlawZeg3jbigerFIFABmD5VQM6lnrFOW1idF5AE/edit?pli=1#gid=1091470126>

⁵⁶ <https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/18vTAvllQdes6Vz3LznX0E28dJsWMxMPv>

⁵⁷

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/temp-form/report/periodic-report_horizon-eu_ratom_en.pdf

⁵⁸ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pagelId=1867970>

⁵⁹ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_Opnl8LfiWNZlgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

- an overview of the progress towards the objectives of the action, including milestones and deliverables identified in Annex 1;
 - an explanation justifying any differences between work expected to be carried out in accordance with Annex 1 and that actually carried out;
 - an overview of the exploitation and dissemination of the results and, if required in Annex 1, an updated 'plan for the exploitation and dissemination of the results'.
 - an overview of the communication activities;
- a summary for publication by the EC;
- the answers to the 'questionnaire', covering issues related to the action implementation and the economic and societal impact, notably in the context of the EC and the Horizon Europe key performance indicators and EC and the Horizon Europe monitoring requirements.

Each partner shall send or provide within the technical report template, as requested, information about the work performed and efforts devoted in the corresponding period to the PM Team, within 30 calendar days after the end of the reporting period. Effort figures can however be requested by the PM Team at any point during the project. For the purpose of accountability, Beneficiaries are requested to keep track of their efforts at the task/activity level. This facilitates the linkage between effort and progress when reporting to the EC.

The Periodic Technical Report template provided by the EC can be found on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁶⁰. This template will be used for each of the two Periodic Technical Reports unless the EC produces an amended version throughout the course of the STEERS project.

Detailed instructions on the submission of the periodic technical report will be provided by the PM Team to all partners in advance of the reporting deadline.

7.3.2. Financial Reporting

Disclaimer: Beneficiaries must always ensure they follow the EC financial reporting guidelines. The details provided here are valid at the date of the document submission but may be superseded by changes to EC rules. See the Financial Reporting Guidelines available on the EC Participant Portal⁶¹ for further information.

As with all EC Horizon Europe projects, each STEERS project Beneficiary has a budget, which comprises the estimated costs that will be incurred during the project lifecycle. These costs can be covered with EC funding. Total funding received by a Beneficiary cannot exceed its costs (i.e. it cannot yield a profit derived from participation in the project).

EC funding follows EC reimbursement rules, which imply in the STEERS project a maximum 80% of the costs reimbursed for eligible project activities. EC funding is paid in several instalments: an advance payment (pre-financing) at the beginning of the project, periodic interim payments reimbursing the costs reported and accepted in each Periodic Report (up to a total amount of 80%

⁶⁰

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1un1AAIBGa8wqE73qIXa5vk8wMeTxeAzU/edit?usp=drive_link&ouid=117088393006618116036&rtpof=true&sd=true

⁶¹ <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders-opportunities/pages/viewpage.action?pagelId=1867970>

of the total funding for a Beneficiary), and a final payment of the remaining 20% of the total funding.

Budgeted efforts and costs are available in the DoA. When agreed by the MB, budgets can be adjusted by transfers of amounts between Beneficiaries or between budget categories (or both) during the project life. This may not require an amendment, if the action is implemented as described in DoA. In case of subcontracting, these costs should be included in the DoA (via Amendment if needed) to make sure they are accepted by the EC as costs claimed.

7.3.2.1. Eligible costs

Costs which are categorised as eligible may be claimed for reimbursement. In order to consider project costs as eligible and therefore be approved by the EC, they must fulfil the following general conditions:

- They must be actually incurred by the Beneficiary;
- They must be incurred in connection with the action as described in the DoA and necessary for its implementation;
- They must be determined in accordance with the usual accounting principles of the Beneficiary;
- They must be incurred during the duration of the project, with the exception of costs relating to the submission of the periodic report for the last reporting period and the final report;
- They must be recorded in the Beneficiaries' accounts;
- They must comply with the applicable national law on taxes, and social security;
- They must be reasonable, justified and must comply with the principle of sound financial management, in particular regarding economy and efficiency;
- They must be indicated in the estimated overall budget in the DoA.

Beneficiaries should take into account, in the day-to-day administration of the project, some practical advice that may facilitate their financial management.

Beneficiaries need to:

- be aware of their own budget distribution;
- coordinate their financial flows: budget, funding, expenditure, justification, payments;
- avoid inconsistencies between efforts spent in the project (recorded in time sheets) and personnel cost justification.

'Budget' refers to costs that each partner is expected to incur, as declared in the DoA. The amount contributed by the EC is called 'funding' or 'EC contribution', and corresponds to 80% of the eligible costs. A Beneficiary has to justify its total budget in order to get the expected funding. The actual costs incurred during the project (the 'practical' implementation of the planned budget) is called the 'expenditure'. These costs will conform to EC rules and therefore be justifiable. Lastly, 'payments' refer to the actual amounts transferred to the partners' accounts

during the project. These depend on the funding of each partner and the justification accepted by the EC, and cannot exceed the total funding of each Beneficiary.

Identification of eligible costs:

Personnel Costs. The EC follows a policy of full cost justification for all Beneficiaries. This means that the hours devoted by all of the personnel involved in a project can be justified, irrespective of them being newly hired for the project or permanent staff.

For the justification of personnel costs in the periodic financial statement, Beneficiaries must take into account the efforts (expressed in person-months) reported for the same period so that these are consistent with the amounts justified. Personnel costs are understood to include salaries, social charges, etc.; all of the actual costs that the person represents for the institution.

The personnel costs are normally calculated by the hourly rate multiplied by the number of actual hours worked for the project.

The hourly rate (based on actual costs) can be calculated as: actual annual personnel costs, divided by the number of annual productive hours. The number of annual productive hours that makes a person-month can vary between partners. All partners must calculate their specific productive hours according to the internal accounting practice for their organisation. In case different categories of personnel have different working conditions, individual productive hours may be calculated. The productive hours per year should exclude annual leave, public holidays, training (if not project related) and sick leave.

In addition, for personnel costs, the Beneficiaries must keep time records for the number of hours declared for all actual work performed for the project. The time records must be in writing and approved by the persons working for the action and their supervisors, at least monthly.

It is advised that time records should include:

- the title and Grant Agreement number of the project, as specified in the GA;
- the Beneficiary's full name, as specified in the GA;
- the full name, date and signature of the person working for the action;
- the number of hours worked for the action in the period covered by the time record; it is highly recommended that the number of hours is detailed per day (hours worked for the action in each day);
- short description of the work carried out during the month;
- the supervisor's full name and signature.

Other direct costs

Travel and subsistence costs

- As a general rule, common meetings expenses (catering, meeting rooms, etc.) shall be paid and justified by the host partner/s in the corresponding reporting period under the “other direct costs” category.
- Travel costs must be needed for the work in the project, or for activities related to it (e.g. presentation of a paper explaining the results of the project in a conference). Travel costs related to a conference where no specific project-related work will be performed or presented by the Beneficiary would not be eligible. Travel costs should be limited to the necessity for the project; any extension of the travel for other professional or private reasons is not an eligible cost.
- Each partner must apply the travel rules of their own organisation (i.e. some organisations reimburse a flat rate allowance for meal expenses while others reimburse actual costs).

The ELIXIR Hub provide decision trees for determining who pays for travel and meeting costs - the hosting organisation or the Beneficiary:

Who pays what? **Event organiser** or **external source**?

Venue costs:

Figure 6. Venue costs decision tree

Travel costs:

Figure 7. Travel costs decision tree

For more information, see ELIXIR’s Guidelines and Tips for Events - for event organisers⁶².

The depreciation costs of equipment, infrastructure or other assets (new or second hand) as recorded in the Beneficiary’s accounts are eligible, if they are purchased and written off in accordance with the Beneficiary’s usual accounting principles. The only portion of the costs that will be taken into account is that which corresponds to the duration of the action and the rate of actual use for the purpose of the action.

Costs of other goods and services (consumables, supplies, dissemination, protection of results, certificates on the financial statements, certificates on the methodology, translations, publications) are eligible if they are purchased specifically for the project.

Subcontracting and other third parties’ costs. Regarding subcontracting costs, it is paramount that the DoA includes a specification that enables approval by the EC.

The EC lay a ground rule that all partners must have the technical and financial resources needed to carry out the project themselves, but if it is necessary to implement the project, a Beneficiary may call upon subcontractors to implement “action tasks” described in Article 9.2 of the Grant Agreement (“Subcontracting”)⁶³.

Indirect costs. Indirect costs or overheads (e.g. heating, lighting, security, office supplies, etc.), which represents a fair apportionment of the overall overheads of the institution, are to be added to the above-mentioned categories. As they are indirect, these costs are not justified using invoices, etc., but are simply stated in the financial statement as a 25% flat rate of the direct costs

⁶² https://docs.google.com/document/d/12YrPswEuUywSRaYdjUDjaq-bvhm_e_gOqd1pM44vmc/edit#

⁶³ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LfiWNZjgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

(except for subcontracting and the costs of resources made available by third parties which are not used on the premises of the Beneficiary, which bear no overheads).

Figure 8. An overview of how to determine a subcontractor, linked third party, third party providing in-kind contributions or in-house consultant.

If in doubt, we encourage you to email STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org for further guidance or clarification.

7.3.2.2. Non-Eligible costs.

Non-Eligible costs: costs which can not be claimed.

The EC state that there are some costs which cannot be considered eligible and therefore, can not be included in the financial statement:

Costs that do not comply with the conditions set out in Articles 6.1 and 6.2 of the Grant Agreement (see Article 6.3 of the GA), in particular:

- Costs related to return on capital
- Debt and service debt charges
- Provisions for possible future losses or charges
- Interest owed
- Currency exchange losses
- Bank costs charged by the Beneficiary's bank for transfers from the Commission
- Excessive or reckless expenditure

- Deductible VAT
- Costs incurred during suspension of the implementation of the action.
- Any costs which do not meet the conditions established in the previous section.

Costs declared under another EU or Euratom grant (including grants awarded by a Member State and financed by the EU or Euratom budget and grants awarded by bodies other than the Commission for the purpose of implementing the EU or Euratom budget); in particular, indirect costs if the Beneficiary is already receiving an operating grant financed by the EU or Euratom budget in the same period, unless it can demonstrate that the operating grant does not cover any costs of the action.

7.3.2.3. Submitting the financial statement

The financial statement is an official statement submitted by the Beneficiary. Any Linked Third Parties (LTP) must provide their financial statement to the project Beneficiary who in turn, must submit the report to the EC on their behalf. In the financial statement the Beneficiary must declare any costs incurred during the specific reporting period for which they wish to be reimbursed by the EC, where applicable.

The EC uses an online application tool called the Funding & Tenders Portal for the submission of financial statements. Each Beneficiary has access to the portal and are expected to submit their costs there.

Cost must be filled in the Funding & Tender Opportunities Portal within 20 calendar days after the end of the reporting period together with the explanation of use of resources. It is advised that Beneficiaries prepare in advance for reporting and liaise with any relevant financial or administrative department in their respective institution at least one month in advance of the end of the reporting period.

Specific guidelines for accessing the Participant Portal will also be provided by the PM Team in the months leading up to the reporting period. These guidelines will include complete instructions and recommendations for adequate reporting.

7.3.2.4. Adjustments to previous periods

Any adjustment (retroactive modification of costs submitted in previous periods) requires the submission of a supplementary Financial statement for the period, where the details of that adjustment will appear.

Together with the new financial statement, the details and justification for the adjustment must be provided by the participant in the periodic report.

Therefore, for correction of financial statements submitted in previous reporting periods, the following need to be submitted:

- One Financial statement for the current period;

- One separate Financial statement for every previous period where adjustments are needed, which will include those adjusted (negative/positive) costs of that specific previous period.

If these costs need to be covered by a Certificate on Financial Statements (CFS), they could be supported within the CFS for the current period but with a specific indication by the auditor certifying both the supplementary costs incurred in previous periods and those claimed in the current one.

7.3.3. Final Report

Within 60 days after the end of the project, and in addition to the periodic report for the last reporting period, the Consortium must also submit a final report to the EC. This final report must include the following:

1. A 'final technical report' with a summary for publication containing:
 - a. an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
 - b. the conclusions on the action, and;
 - c. the socio-economic impact of the action.
2. A 'final financial report' containing:
 - a. a 'final summary financial statement', created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance and;
 - b. a 'certificate on the financial statements' for each Beneficiary, if it requests a total contribution of €430,000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices.

This final report will be prepared by the PM Team and the MB with input from all WPs.

The PM Team will also coordinate the elaboration of the final financial report that accompanies the technical report and in which reported figures from all participants throughout the project are consolidated.

Detailed instructions on the submission of the final report will be provided by the PM Team to all partners in advance of the reporting deadline.

7.3.4. Certificate on the Financial Statement (CFS)

A certificate on the financial statement (CFS), also named audit certificate, is a statement from a competent auditor in which correctness and compliance with EC rules of a cost justification is certified.

A CFS must be submitted together with the corresponding financial cost statement at the end of the project by all Beneficiaries if the Beneficiary requests a total contribution of 430,000 Euro or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices.

Auditors eligible to deliver audit certificates must be “external auditors” or “public competent officers” who are “independent” and “qualified to carry out statutory audits of accounting documents”. It is highly recommended to determine an adequate auditor well before the end of the reporting period to ensure his/her availability for a timely generation of the audit certificate.

For more information regarding the CFS, see:

- Article 24.2 of the STEERS Grant Agreement⁶⁴

7.3.5. EC Funding

The EC funding is paid to the Coordinator (ELIXIR Hub), who distributes it to the Beneficiaries without unjustified delay.

Some general rules apply with respect to the payments:

- The EC paid a pre-financing amount at the start of the project which was distributed to the Beneficiaries receiving funding;
- Interim payments will be depending on costs justified and accepted after each reporting period, and distributed after receipt from the EC;
- A final payment will be released by the EC corresponding to the costs accepted for the last reporting period, plus any adjustment needed.

Total payments during the project cannot exceed 85% of the total funding. 15% of the funding will only be paid after final reports are approved.

The most important notion for Beneficiaries to bear in mind is that payments follow costs reported – and costs reported follow work done for the project. The Coordinator has the right to reject costs reported by any Beneficiary if they are not in line with the work performed.

7.3.6. Receipts of the project

The receipts (in lay terms, ‘income received due to the project’) of the project are:

- Resources **made available by third parties to the partner** by means of financial transfers or contributions in-kind which are free of charge:
 - Shall be considered a receipt of the project if they have been contributed by the third party specifically to be used on the project.
 - Shall not be considered a receipt of the project if their use is at the discretion of the participant's management.
- **Income generated by the project:**
 - Shall be considered a receipt for the participant when generated by actions undertaken in carrying out the project and from the sale of assets purchased under the grant agreement up to the value of the cost initially charged to the project by the participant;

⁶⁴ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_Opnl8LfIWNZlgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

- Shall not be considered a receipt for the participant when generated from the research use or direct exploitation of foreground resulting from the project.

7.4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The outcomes and impact of the project in relation to the call text will be assessed against Key Performance Indicators (See table 17). Relating to all WPs, these KPIs can easily be monitored, from the project onset and will be refined in Task 5.3. Progress against these KPIs must be reported to the governance boards, to inform project planning and management, looking forwards (rather than post-hoc assessment), ensuring corrective actions are taken as and when they are needed. Some of these indicators already form part of ELIXIR’s suite of indicators, which are used to monitor the infrastructure’s performance (mostly internally-facing) and impact (mostly externally-facing), in line with ESFRI’s current work on ensuring that the infrastructures it has recognised are adequately monitored.

A full list of the KPIs as identified in the Description of Action Part B⁶⁵ can be viewed in the table below:

Table 17. STEERS KPIs.

Expected Impact (Call text) and ELIXIR-STEERS approach to deliver and go beyond
Increased long-term sustainability of European RIs
<p>ELIXIR is one of the largest ‘ESFRI’ RIs in terms of Membership size, being distributed in 22 countries and involving more than 240 research institutes. ELIXIR’s operational structures⁵⁵, extensive communications and dissemination channels, and core funding will be mobilised to amplify project results.</p> <p>Furthermore, much knowledge-exchange and experience-sharing takes place through participation in operational structures, which are open to all ELIXIR Members (and beyond in the case of ELIXIR Communities). Planned outreach with Croatia, Poland, Romania, Austria, and Slovakia will lead to several additional countries joining ELIXIR, supporting sustainability further</p> <p>Baseline and assumptions: Not all ELIXIR Nodes are at the same maturity stages, nor do they all benefit from the same level of national-level financing. ELIXIR has already started to equip some of its Nodes with ‘key to sustainability’ skills such as for engaging with funders and policy-makers, for assessing and demonstrating impact.</p>
New services available to a wider user community, including participants in other parts of Horizon Europe, allowing to better tackle scientific and societal challenges

⁶⁵ <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1K66wz0jDS3K6VypdzyV67PgAIMPpKduW>

<p>ELIXIR has 15 Communities that will be targeted as potential adopters/implementers of the technical toolkit (incl. guidelines and recommendations) and solutions, both developed by WP2 and WP3. ELIXIR Community engagement efforts and the level of adoption/implementation will be monitored/reported on through indicators. Dedicated outreach events in WP5 (T5.3) will ensure that policy-makers in other parts of Horizon Europe are aware of the free services that ELIXIR offers</p> <p>Baseline and assumptions: ELIXIR Communities are an operational structure of ELIXIR; hence project participants will have direct access to them and will be able to use existing relationship capital to collaborate</p>
<p>Better structured and strengthened European RI landscape</p>
<p>New countries will join ELIXIR as Members, and collaborations with other ESFRI RIs will be set up and/or strengthened. Here again, the size/distributed nature of ELIXIR will be used to amplify project effects relating to the professionalisation of ELIXIR Node operation/management (and similarly for the capacity to provide technical training)</p> <p>Baseline and assumptions: ELIXIR has already much invested in the professionalisation of its RI staff in Nodes, for instance through the EMMRI masters as well as complementary core-funded career development activities and formal training courses</p>
<p>Increased capacity to address EU policy priorities and/or support EU industry</p>
<p>Industry engagement events will be run, and collaborations with industry will be stimulated</p> <p>Baseline and assumptions: ELIXIR has an existing and dynamic industry engagement programme and dedicated webpage with up-to-date activities, complemented by a dynamic Industry Focus Group59, well attended across the ELIXIR Membership</p>
<p>Reduction of environmental (including climate-related) impacts as well as optimisation of resource and energy consumption integrated through the full life cycle of RIs</p>
<p>The level of adoption/implementation of energy-related aspects of the technical toolkit and solutions will be monitored/reported on through indicators</p> <p>Baseline and assumptions: This is an entirely new area of work for ELIXIR</p>
<p>Reinforced global competitiveness of the European Research Area</p>
<p>There will be international outreach in countries beyond Europe (specifically Latin America and Africa), which reinforce ELIXIR's position as a RI of global significance</p> <p>Baseline and assumptions: ELIXIR services are already used by millions across the world, but it is not always known that these services are provided under the ELIXIR umbrella.</p>

In addition, Communications KPIs are detailed in ELIXIR Communications Strategy⁶⁶.

During the monthly Managing Board (WPLs) Meetings the KPI should be reviewed and updated as part of the rolling agenda.

The KPIs must be formally reviewed and updated as part of:

- M1.2 Project KPIs presented to MB - Month 12
- D1.3 Project Handbook V2 - Month 12
- M1.3 Final project KPIs presented to MB - Month 24
- D1.6 Project Handbook v3 - Month 24

As and when new metrics are available, it is the responsibility of the WPLs to inform the PM Team who will then include them in the dashboard to be monitored monthly.

8. DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The Data Management Plan (DMP) will be defined and updated throughout the project lifecycle as part of Task 1.3. The initial version of the DMP must be created by the ELIXIR Hub in the first six months of the project within WP1 (D1.2) according to the project scope, the EC requirements and recommendations as well as the ELIXIR position paper on FAIR data management. Ethical and legal compliance measures will be considered when developing the DMP and it will be updated on a regular basis to capture the relevant changes. The FAIR compliant DMP will incorporate relevant project components from each WP, while taking necessary restrictions into account. External projects using project results will have their own DMP.

Any questions regarding the DMP should be directed to the ELIXIR Hub (juan.arenas@elixir-europe.org).

9. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Whilst the scientific focus on ELIXIR-STEERS is on enabling analysis of data through the provision of software and workflows and the collation of best practice recommendations for the community to use, ELIXIR-STEERS itself will generate no new data for the purposes of research at any level. No experiments will be carried out and there are no activities foreseen that will require ethical approval at the institutional level of the partners involved. The project will generate other research assets (e.g. standards guidelines, software, workflow descriptions) none of which are foreseen to contain "personal data". These research assets will be published as "open data" in accordance with the data management plan.

⁶⁶ <https://elixir-europe.org/documents/elixir-communications-strategy>

Personal data will be collected or generated in the context of what is necessary for effective project management, e.g. mailing lists and registration details of project partners attending project workshops and meetings, including name, dietary preferences and gender (for reporting purposes).

When personal data are collected by project partners, the respective data controllers will adhere to GDPR at all times, following their institutional processes and practices. They will only be stored for the duration needed and will not be used for purposes beyond the effective operation of the ELIXIR-STEERS project.

ELSI expertise on AI will be ensured via the external, independent Ethics Advisor, who will be appointed to advise the project, as well as more general ethics advice via the ELIXIR SAB.

WP₁ will deliver a DMP (D1.2), in collaboration with WPs 2 & 3, to provide further evidence of appropriate ethics committees and competent authorities. ELIXIR SAB includes ethics experts who will be consulted on this specific deliverable.

As ELIXIR-STEERS does not handle private data or highly sensitive data, most of the requirements that will apply to projects dealing with research or secondary use data are not relevant here. However, the STEERS project will undergo continual Ethics reviews as needed throughout the project and at a minimum, in line with the periodic reporting schedule following EC Horizon Europe guidelines.

For more information regarding ethics within the STEERS project, see:

- P30 of the Description of Action, Part B, Section 4.1 Ethics⁶⁷

9.1. Equal Opportunities

In accordance with Article 14 - Ethics and Values, and Annex 5 (page 3), of the Grant Agreement⁶⁸, The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level.

ELIXIR-STEERS will be mindful of the gender dimension throughout the project's activities as well as in the composition of the consortium and this will be specifically tackled by Task 1.5 Excellence in Management (in collaboration with WP₄) where there is a dedicated deliverable that will incorporate learnings from the ELIXIR Nodes in terms of Gender Equality Plans and specific initiatives to develop a common strategy representing ELIXIR's values (D1.5 ELIXIR Gender Equality Strategy).

Gender balance and diversity has already been considered within ELIXIR when setting up ELIXIR's governance structure. ELIXIR's Equal Opportunities Strategy has been in place since 2018⁶⁹ (an

⁶⁷ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1j5BhfCgcFS0kqm1igw9S1XCbkuSnj18S/view?usp=drive_link

⁶⁸ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LfIWNZlgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

⁶⁹ Gater C. ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy. F1000Research 2018, 7 (ELIXIR):1234: <https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1115874.1>

output of the ELIXIR-EXCELERATE project) and is designed to inform the ELIXIR Handbook of Operations. It covers recommendations on equal opportunities for the ELIXIR Hub and Nodes, and it outlines the data and metrics that the Hub and Nodes are recommended to collect in relation to equality and diversity. It covers the cycle for data collection, monitoring and feeding this back into practice. It also describes a method for establishing an ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Toolkit, collaborations with other networks and projects and outlines the path to a formal ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Policy.

Of particular relevance to the implementation of STEERS are the following aspects:

- Equality is taken into account in all events by providing statistics and adopting action plans (e.g. speaker balance, training opportunities) as set out by the Equal Opportunities Strategy⁷⁰ and ELIXIR Handbook of Operations⁷¹ (e.g. guidelines on workshop organisation).
- The ELIXIR Hub Code of Conduct⁷² is in place at all ELIXIR Hub organised and/or funded events
- To address the gender balance and help build a cadre of diverse future leaders we specifically encourage female scientists and other underrepresented groups to apply and participate in user training, workshops, and hackathons and must monitor this via KPIs to track progress (Equality KPIs are part of the formally adopted ELIXIR Training metrics)
- We are particularly aware that personal situations can seriously restrict mobility, including attending meetings and training events, of some staff and user scientists. In this light, we must devise research and training opportunities compatible with the personal circumstances of each researcher, benefiting both female and male scientists (e.g. EMBL-EBI has successfully used avatars to provide scientists with young family remote training opportunities⁷³).
- The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy highlights the issue of unconscious bias in institutional procedures and recommend implementation of good practice (e.g. LIBRA handbook⁷⁴). We will provide unconscious bias training as part of management training (WP₄).
- The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities strategy sets out recommendations for accessibility of online tools and services⁷⁵; ELIXIR-STEERS must adhere to these recommendations as part of overall attention to user experience.

For more information regarding all equal opportunity matters within the STEERS project, see:

- the STEERS Grant Agreement⁷⁶ articles listed below:
 - Article 14.2 Values
 - Annex 5 (page 3)
- the STEERS DoA, Part B⁷⁷:

⁷⁰ <https://f1000research.com/documents/7-1234>

⁷¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/handbook-operations>

⁷² <https://elixir-europe.org/events/code-of-conduct>

⁷³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/about/news/announcements/bioinformatics-training-with-robot-avatars>

⁷⁴ <https://www.eu-libra.eu/news/libra-recruitment-handbook>

⁷⁵ E.g. by following W3C best practice: <https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/>

⁷⁶ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8LfWNZJgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

⁷⁷ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1j5BhfCgcFS0kqm1igw9S1XCbkuSnjl8S/view?usp=drive_link

- Section 1.2.5 Gender dimension
- The ELIXIR Equal Opportunities Strategy⁷⁸

10. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

For all matters relating to Intellectual Property Rights please refer to:

1. Section 8 of the STEERS Consortium Agreement⁷⁹
2. Article 16.4 'Specific rules on IPR, results and background' and Annex 5 (pages 3-10) of the STEERS Grant Agreement⁸⁰

Or contact the PMT: STEERS-coordination@elixir-europe.org

ANNEX 1: PROJECT GANTT CHART

WP/ Task #	Task Description	Lead	M0 3	M0 6	M0 9	M1 2	M1 5	M1 8	M2 1	M2 4	M2 7	M3 0	M3 3	M3 6
WP1 Biodiversity Genome Europe														
		ELIXIR Hub												
T1.1	Project mobilisation and guidance - adoption of project management boards, governance & internal project communication	ELIXIR Hub												
T1.2	Project monitoring and support	ELIXIR Hub												
T1.3	Development and implementation of a project data management plan and correlated activities	ELIXIR Hub												
T1.4	Development of long-term sustainability plan for project outputs	ELIXIR Hub												
T1.5	Excellence in Management	ELIXIR Hub												
Implementation of research software best practices through ELIXIR														
WP2 Communities														
T2.1	Building the technical toolkit for software best-practices	UNIPD												
T2.2	Identifying efficiency indicators for research software and workflows	CERTH												

⁷⁸ <https://f1000research.com/documents/7-1234>

⁷⁹ As of 16th April 2024 the Consortium Agreement is in draft

⁸⁰ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1T-i9aaOg8NpW0_OpnL8lfiWNZlgt6-sv/view?usp=drive_link

T2.3	Adoption of best practices through Community engagement	UL	
WP3 Infrastructure services to enable adoption and deployment of software best practices			
T3.1	Enabling crediting scientists for research artefacts	ATHENA RC	
T3.2	Contributing towards sustainable research software through Software Management Plans	UOCHB	
T3.3	Identify fit-for-purpose reproducible workflows through technical and scientific benchmarking	BSC	
T3.4	Integrating optimisation criteria for environmental impact in commonly used workflow management systems	Earlham	
WP4 Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training			
T4.1	Embedding good practices in ELIXIR Node structures	UiB	
T4.2	Organisational and research management capacity for Nodes	biodata.pt	
T4.3	Capacity building in training skills for Node staff	UU	
WP5 Communications, outreach, industry and international			
T5.1	Delivering world-class communications activities	ELIXIR Hub	
T5.2	Facilitate industry engagement with a particular focus on SMEs	ELIXIR Hub	
T5.3	Expand country Membership and outreach to EU funders	ELIXIR Hub	
T5.4	Collaborate with research infrastructures, projects and initiatives in Europe and internationally	ELIXIR Hub	
WP6 Ethics requirements			
T6.1	Ensure compliance with the 'ethics requirements' set out in this work package	ELIXIR Hub	

The full project GANTT chart and other project planning information can be found in the Project Master File on the STEERS Google Shared Drive⁸¹. Please note that this is kept as at the proposal stage (not updated)

⁸¹ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1KzS6gt9O7YyD6DEabdGWiuKZxZ-iKtErY4PpSdH_mMI/edit#gid=1398154277

Appendix 2: ELIXIR-STEERS Project Handbook - live version

The Project Handbook is accessible to all project Partners on the ELIXIR-STEERS Google Drive: [ELIXIR-STEERS PROJECT HANDBOOK](#)⁸²

⁸² ELIXIR-STEERS Project Handbook: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bcB9lt5r_1lfPVeFCzgLUyoY3zKKEGalHfCbhFLYZug/edit

